

graphia

GRAPHIA

Knowledge Graphs, AI Services and Next Generation Instrumentation for R&D in Social Sciences and Humanities

Work Package WP6

Innovation Management, Communications and Industry Engagement

Deliverable D6.2

Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan

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List of Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AI4LAM	Artificial Intelligence for Libraries, Archives & Museums
AIOTI	Alliance for Internet of Things Innovation
API	Application Programming Interface
ATRIUM	Advancing Frontier Research in the Arts and Humanities
AU	Abertay University
B/T/S	Base/Target/Stretch
CC-BY	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License
CNR	The National Research Council
CNRS	National Centre for Scientific Research
CAF	CONNECT Advisory Forum
DEC Plan	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan
DoA	Description of Action
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERA	European Research Area
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EXYGEN	Explore Your Graphs Engine
FAIR	Findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable
FASCA	Facilitating Scholarly Communication Analysis through GoTriple Pipeline
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General data protection regulation
GRAPHIA	Knowledge Graphs, AI Services and Next Generation Instrumentation for R&D in Social Sciences and Humanities
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HRP	Horizon Results Platform
IBL PAN	The Institute of Literary Research
ICF	Industry Commons Foundation
IMeTo	Impact Measurement Tool
IP	Intellectual property
IPL	Innovation Prototyping Lab
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
JUST	Judicious, Unbiased, Safe, Transparent principles

KER	Key Exploitable Result
KNAW	Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
LLM	Large Language Models
LLM4SSH	Large language models for social sciences and humanities
LUH	Leibniz University Hannover
LUMEN	Linked User-Driven Multidisciplinary Exploration Network
M	Month
NLP	Natural Language Processing
OA	Open Access
OISPG	Open Innovation Strategy and Policy Group
PN	Pelagios Network
PPTs	PowerPoint Presentations
PSNC	Institute of Bioorganic Chemistry
QUAGGA	Question Answering over Graphs
R&D	Research & development
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
e-SDF	e-Science Data Factory
SKG-IF	Scientific Knowledge Graph – Interoperability Framework
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
SSHOC	SSH Open Marketplace
SME	Small to Medium Enterprises
SPARQL	Standard semantic query language and protocol
TIB	Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology University Library
UNIBO	Bologna University
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The GRAPHIA Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan (DEC) outlines the strategic framework for how the project communicates its objectives, engages stakeholders and ensures the long-term uptake and impact of its results. Developed under Work Package (WP) 6, its first version was published in June 2025 as a plan that guides the activities of all project partners involved in raising awareness, fostering collaboration, and enabling exploitation of GRAPHIA's outputs. This, month (M) 18, version is the first update.

GRAPHIA is a Horizon Europe project aiming at enhancing research infrastructure for the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) through the development of a knowledge graph, artificial intelligence (AI) services, and next-generation research instrumentation. The DEC Plan aligns communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities with this mission, ensuring that outputs are findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable (FAIR), and sustainable beyond the project duration.

The plan identifies and engages three primary stakeholder groups: academia and scholarly communication actors, industry, and public-sector organisations. Dissemination efforts are driven by a central website, complemented by Zenodo and Zotero repositories, publications, blog posts, events, and cross-project collaborations. Communication activities leverage social media (primarily LinkedIn and Bluesky), newsletters, and targeted messaging to promote GRAPHIA's innovations.

Exploitation is structured around the Key Exploitable Results (KERs), including the SSH Knowledge Graph, large language models for social sciences and humanities (LLM4SSH), advanced instrumentation prototypes, an SSH citations index, an interoperability framework, and real-world use cases. Each KER is accompanied by tailored exploitation paths, licensing strategies (primarily open-source), and integration plans with infrastructures, i.e. European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), SSH Open Marketplace (SSHOC) and others.

The plan also details mechanisms for sustainability, including governance models, open repositories, and institutional commitments to hosting and curating outputs. Innovation Prototyping Labs (IPLs) serve as key engagement points for stakeholder validation and feedback, linking exploitation strategy with community needs.

This report is complemented by deliverable 6.1 [Communications Kit](#) developed separately that provides an overview of items available to all project partners for download. This deliverable 6.2 is a living document that will be updated during project implementation and tailored to the project's needs and progress on demand (at M18 with this current version, and at M36). All the data related to key performance indicators (KPIs) numbers achieved by M18 and presented in the related deliverable 6.2 update was recorded on 16th June 2026.

1. Introduction

The major impact of the GRAPHIA project will be to boost the excellence of the European Research Area (ERA) by developing a Knowledge Graph for SSH augmented with advanced AI services while upgrading next-generation instrumentation for research & development (R&D) in SSH. Through these innovative solutions and an Interoperability Framework, GRAPHIA will address societal challenges with some of the most demanding applications in SSH. The expected impact is set by the work that will be carried out through the project's seven KERs listed below and described in more detail in the exploitation section three of this document:

- SSH Knowledge Graph.
- LLM4SSH.
- Catalogue for Next-Generation Technological Instruments and Data Lifecycle Management Workflows for SSH (previously named as 'Prototypes for Next-Generation SSH Instruments').
- SSH Citations Index.
- Technical Interoperability Framework.
- Real-World Use Cases Implementation.
- Question Answering over Graphs (Quagga) (a new KER established later in the project)

A successful strategy to maximise impact within the GRAPHIA project relies on understanding the diversity, complexity and fragility of the landscape. It needs to take into consideration the dynamic nature of research, linguistic diversity, stakeholder types involved, the private and public dimensions of collaboration, interoperability, standardisation, as well as many other factors. In particular, the communication and dissemination actions are necessary to create awareness about the project's goals, improve collaboration between private and public stakeholder types, support the training and onboarding activities and provide spaces for open discussions. Additionally, an engagement-based methodology in the form of training, onboarding, IPLs with co-located conference elements will be supported by the dissemination and communication activities, which will ensure that the targeted stakeholders are in fact engaged from the outset of the project. This will support an exploitation plan ensuring the successful uptake and usage of the project's outputs. Dedicated measures and indicators have been created to quantify the impact of DEC

activities, as outlined in the sections that follow. This will further guarantee the adoption of the SSH knowledge graph and other results, increasing alignment on research in Europe and beyond. As part of the DEC activities, the specific target audiences have been identified based on the target groups for the project overall, as per figure 1.

Figure 1. GRAPHIA stakeholders

The target groups were identified with the collaboration between all project partners during the project proposal writing phase, where all the partners provided input in a Google Doc listing the stakeholders they collaborate with or are in contact with. These were then mapped into three main umbrella groups: academia & scholarly communication; industry; society and public organisations. Some stakeholder types will overlap given the nature of their work; for example, Research Funding Organisations (RFOs) also play the role of policymakers on occasion, libraries often have publishing activities, and so on. This has been taken into account when establishing the activities in the next sections to ensure they are efficient and effective. A matrix has been created to surface different messaging approaches depending on the challenges each stakeholder group faces, the full list of messages per objectives and stakeholder types has been included in the [Communication Kit](#) (deliverable 6.1). This was further developed by adding concrete contacts to the mapping document later on called stakeholder registry as the project progressed and started disseminating first outcomes as well as participating in internal and external events. To this day we have over 120 contacts in the stakeholder registry document. Given that it contains data under the general data protection regulation (GDPR), the document itself cannot be shared publicly however all the partners were asked to

contribute to it and it has been kept up to date to have a realistic overview of the engagement activities. More information is provided in section 3.7 *Progress on Engagement, Outreach and Commercialisation* as a result of Task 6.3 activities overview.

Additionally, it is important to note that the Base-Target-Stretch (B/T/S) approach has been used to set the KPIs for each of the action points to aim at the target, but also consider what can be achieved if there are more resources available.

The following GRAPHIA partners are part of the dissemination, exploitation and communication activities within WP6:

WP6 GRAPHIA Partners					
OPERAS	Cyprus Institute	GESIS	IBL PAN	ICF	Genius Loci
Abertay University	KNAW	NET7	Odoma	E-SDF	PSNC

Table 1. WP6 Project partners

While only a selection of project partners are taking part in the WP6, the rest of the consortium has also been (and will continue to be) participating in relevant activities through:

- Using their own social media channels.
- Publishing their own blog posts and scientific publications.
- Organising events.
- Taking part in 3rd-party events.
- Other activities as the needs arise.

2. Dissemination

The overarching information hub for GRAPHIA is the dedicated project's [website](#), which links the different resources relevant to all the stakeholder groups and creates recognisable branding. Other dissemination measures will entail different types of publications to share the outcome of the activities, as well as recommendations. The actions comprise approaches, tools, indicators and target groups listed in table 2

below. Besides the website, other mechanisms will also be used that will help target different audiences:

- Other information hubs ([Zenodo](#) community, Zotero space).
- Publications ([blog posts](#), non-peer reviewed articles, scientific publications, policy briefs).
- Events (organised by the project and 3rd-party event participation).
- Guidelines and toolkits.
- Cross-project [collaboration](#).

Target Group: All stakeholder groups			
Action 1: Website creation and curation			
Approach	Channels/Tools	Indicators	Progress so far
A website was created dedicated to the project using a chosen branding (logo, font, colours) that serves as a central online hub to share information about the project, its updates, activities and news.	Website	# of visits per month B:100/T:150/S:200	7662 total ~425 per month
Action 2: Publications			
Approach	Channels/Tools	Indicators	Progress so far
Scientific publications will be submitted for publication during the project to share the outcomes of its activities within the scientific communities and industry.	Scientific journals	# of publications B:2/T:3/S:4	1 published 6 submitted
Policy briefs will be published to share the outputs, recommendations and technical developments.	Zenodo and website	# of policy briefs B:2/T:3/S:4	1st will be submitted soon
Video recordings from workshops, webinars, and other events have been and will be shared to amplify the outreach.	YouTube/ Website	# of views B:400/T:500/S:600	1425 views

Action 3: Deliverables and resources publication			
Approach	Channels/Tools	Indicators	Progress so far
A Zenodo community has been created to publish all the project deliverables and other resources.	Zenodo Community	# of views B:400/T:500/S:600	4043
Action 4: Final event			
Approach	Channels/Tools	Indicators	Progress so far
A final co-located event will be organised in collaboration with a hosting partner at the end of the project.	In-person meeting and sessions	# of participants B:40/T:50/S:60	Not applicable until year 3
Action 5: Workshops, webinars & trainings			
Approach	Channels/Tools	Indicators	Progress so far
Each WP has and will lead and coordinate its own workshops, webinars and trainings with the support of WP6 to disseminate the findings and outputs.	In-person or online meetings and sessions	# of workshops, webinars, trainings B:10/T:12/S:14	21
Action 6: 3rd party events			
Approach	Channels/Tools	Indicators	Progress so far
In order to disseminate the project outputs effectively, partners have and will engage in 3rd party events with presentations, posters, panel discussions and similar.	Proposals to 3rd party events	# of events the project is included in B:10/T:15/S:20	25
Action 7: IPLs			
Approach	Channels/Tools	Indicators	Progress so far
3 multi-day IPLs hosted by ESFRI institutional members, co-located with partner meetings, inviting pilots and use	In-person labs, hybrid conf., video diss., live stream, YouTube	# of total participants for the IPLs B:40/T:60/S:80	125

cases, including a hybrid conference element.			
Target Group: Public Authorities, Industry, Scholarly Communication			
Action 1: Legal guidelines			
Approach	Channels/Tools	Indicators	Progress so far
PDF package with recommendations and templates with the legal guidelines will be created.	Project website	# of views B:100/T:150/S:200	Not applicable at this point
Action 2: Data space connection toolkit			
Approach	Channels/Tools	Indicators	Progress so far
PDF package incl. resources developed during the project exploring the connection between a KG and a data space.	Project website	# of views B:100/T:150/S:200	Not applicable at this point
Action 3: Publications			
Approach	Channels/Tools	Indicators	Progress so far
Industrial Use Cases Digital Hub showcasing the plans and findings of the use cases.	Website	# of views B:200/T:250/S:300	187
Blog posts to share the outcomes of its activities with the rest of the communities affected by the project.	All partners' blog channels	# of blog posts B:14/T:16/S:18	23

Table 2. Dissemination measures and respective KPIs

While it was initially predicted that the website would be ready by M3, due to development delays, it was launched in M4, which has resulted in the monitoring of monthly visitors starting from M5.

2.1 Information Hubs

2.1.1 Website

The GRAPHIA website is the overarching information hub, linking the different resources relevant to all the stakeholder groups within the recognisable branding. It

features a landing page with a short overview of the project and its partners. The menu at the top provides more details on the subpages relevant to:

- Specific objectives and aims as part of the results subpage.
- More information on the consortium.
- Industrial use cases digital hub.
- Blog posts.
- Video resources.
- Events calendar.
- How to contact the project.

Figure 2. Landing page of the GRAPHIA website

After the initial launch, the website has been updated and enriched as the project progressed and more information as well as results were made available. This will continue through the rest of the project. The dedicated [Zenodo](#) community is linked to the website, and a dedicated email address (contact@graphia-ssh.eu) has been created to facilitate communication with the public.

The website is hosted on WordPress through OPERAS and was developed together with the DrawingArt company. For monitoring purposes, Google Analytics is used to keep track of monthly unique visitors. Additionally, a mailing list [sign-up form](#) has been created for stakeholders who wish to stay updated on project activities, events and similar information via email.

GRAPHIA website monthly visitors have grown steadily as per the below table. It is normal to expect a lower number during the months of summer or winter holidays, but that is recovered by the more active months with events and news that are published accordingly.

Month	Visitors
April 2025	201
May 2025	472
June 2025	100
July 2025	124
August 2025	91
September 2025	629
October 2025	995
November 2025	305
December 2025	467
January 2026	610
February 2026	860
March 2026	563
April 2026	548
May 2026	913
June 2026 (recorded on 16th June)	784

Table 3. GRAPHIA website monthly visitors

This brings the total number of visitors to 7662. As part of the mailing list, we also achieved a good number of subscribers that is currently at 393.

The screenshot shows the OpenEdition Groups interface for the mailing list `graphia-news@groups.openedition.org`. The subject is "Mailing list for GRAPHIA news". The interface is divided into two main sections: a left sidebar and a main content area.

Left Sidebar:

- Owner, Subscriber: Ursula Rabar
- List Options**
- Subscribers: 393 (Error rate: 3%)
- Owners: karla.avanco, mandy.lin, maxim.kupreyev, sy.holsinger, ursula.rabar
- Moderators: (same as owners)
- Contact owners
- List Home
- Admin**
- Moderate
- Statistics
- Subscriber Options
- Unsubscribe
- Archive
- Post

Main Content Area:

- Basic Operations**
- Buttons: Edit List Config, Users, Blacklist, Manage Archives, Bounces, Logs
- Manage list members**
- Administrative Options**
- Buttons: Pending subscriptions, Pending unsubscriptions, Blacklist, Bounces, Dump, Exclude
- Subscription reminder message**
- Button: Remind all
- Add Subscribers**
- Text: To add an individual user:

Figure 3. Subscribers to the GRAPHIA mailing list

The Industrial Use Cases Digital Hub

The industrial use cases digital hub (or [Industry Hub](#)), launched in M18, has been one of the major new updates to the website in its second year so far. It contains use cases from commercial, private as well as public organisations working with or providing services to commercial organisations. The scope was and still is (as the hub is a living space that is being upgraded with new use cases continuously) to showcase how these organisations see the project: what is the benefit for them in participating, which challenges it helps address, and similar. To date we have 12 use cases included in the hub with ongoing discussion with other organisations to be added as well. To date there are 187 views of the hub. In the Grant Agreement (GA) it is mentioned that we will be monitoring the downloads, however for visibility reasons and to make the use cases as findable as possible, we have decided to publish them all as part of the website and monitor the page views instead. The collection of the use cases was achieved through various methods: IPLs, a call for pilots (that is further explained in section 2.5 *Open Calls for Participation*), through in person conversations at events and similar. All the partners were asked to provide contacts and connections they believe would be interested in this.

Figure 4. GRAPHIA Industry Hub

The hub was developed in collaboration with the same designer commissioned for the creation of the GRAPHIA website to make sure the branding is consistent across all of our communications.

2.1.2 Zenodo Community and Zotero Space

In order to keep interested stakeholders informed about the project outputs and to provide a dedicated space for deliverables, a GRAPHIA [Zenodo](#) community has been established. It includes various materials, such as (but not limited to):

- Project deliverables (example [D2.2 Technical Architecture](#)).
- PowerPoint presentations (example [webinar presentation](#)).
- Datasets (example [GoTriple metadata dataset](#)).
- Other outputs as they are developed (example [GRAPHIA infographic](#)).
- IPL events containing the link to all the resources (example from [IPL 2025](#) created in collaboration with the LUMEN project).

So far the views and downloads of all the records amount to: 4043 views, 5304 downloads (the full list of records is provided in Appendix table *7.1 Zenodo Records*).

Zenodo provides a reliable platform for preserving and archiving research outputs, ensuring they remain accessible and usable over the long term. It facilitates open

access in a FAIR compliant way to research data, publications, and other scholarly outputs, making them freely available to the global research community.

For internal purposes, a Zotero community has been created to collect, organise, and cite research sources, serving as a tool for project partners to use in their collaborative or individual work.

2.2 Publications

As part of the dissemination activities, various publications have been and will be made publicly available across the different channels and information hubs.

Scientific publications have and will continue to be submitted to open access (OA) journals where possible to present data gathered, technical developments and other relevant findings within the scientific communities and industry. While the aim is to publish at least two scientific publications for the duration of the project, the project partners will endeavour to produce more.

As per the current status shown in the table below, we have one scientific publication published and six submitted for review and publication.

Title	Authors	Status	Publication date	Link
Benchmarking Large Language Models on Reference Extraction and Parsing in the Social Sciences and Humanities	Yurui Zhu, Giovanni Colavizza and Matteo Romanello	Published	13/03/2026	https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-4187/full-02.pdf
From fragmentation to federation: bridging heterogeneous SSH knowledge graphs through query mediation in GRAPHIA	Julien Homo, Kévin Darty, Luca De Santis, Silvio Peroni, Matteo Romanello, Tomasz Hoffmann, Arkadiusz Margraf, Sy Holsinger, Maxim Kupreyev, Ursula	Submitted	Not yet available	Not yet available

	Rabar, Florian Lemoine, Yann Le Franc, Jan Wiebelitz, Benjamin Zapilko			
A W7 structured metadata framework for reinforcing data provenances in 2D/3D	Anthony Pamart, Quentin Vogel, Eloi Gattet, Daouda Ngom, Laurent Bergerot	Submitted	Not yet available	Not yet available
Why citation processing remains challenging in SSH publications: toward a robust and scalable GRAPHIA Citation Index API	Matteo Romanello, Yurui Zhu, Noushin Najafiragheb, Patryk Hubar-Kołodziejczyk, Marta Soricetti, Angelo Di Iorio, Julien Homo	Submitted	Not yet available	Not yet available
CEC: A Tool for Context-Aware Citation Extraction and Citation Intent Classification from Scholarly PDFs	Angelo Di Iorio, Ivan Heibi, Silvio Peroni, Lorenzo Paolini, Marta Soricetti	Submitted	Not yet available	Not yet available
Designing Human-LLM Collaboration by Preserving a Human Locus of Agency in Qualitative Analysis	Crystal Silver, Alex Fawzi, Diane Morrow, Stefano De Paoli	Submitted	Not yet available	Not yet available
The middle-space: an evolution of AI-collaborative design practices for HCD design element generation through the lens of research discovery	Diane Morrow, Crystal Silver, Stefano De Paoli	Submitted	Not yet available	Not yet available

Table 4. Scientific publications

Policy briefs will be published to share the outputs, recommendations and technical developments following the standard European Commission (EC) template. The aim is to publish at least two policy briefs in the three project years, however, if possible and relevant, more will be published.

To date, one policy brief is being prepared to be submitted at the end of June to the EC and published afterwards in our Zenodo community.

Blog posts are an important part of the GRAPHIA website, with [many already released](#) covering topics from the project launch, IPLs, stakeholder oriented reflections, user experience and similar. At the same time, project partners published their own blog posts as they saw fit and in the language of their preference. The full list is available in the Appendix table *7.2 Blog Posts*. As of 16th June 2026 we have 23 blog posts published.

On top of the scientific publications and blog posts, there were 12 news articles published during the 2025 IPL in local online newspapers such as [LIDER](#), [FORBES](#), [ICT Business](#) and others.

Video recordings are not the typical publication format, however, they help in providing a different medium for the audience that prefers to digest project information that way. While it was mentioned in the first deliverable 6.2 version that the videos will be uploaded as a dedicated GRAPHIA playlist via the OPERAS YouTube channel, a decision was made to create a dedicated GRAPHIA YouTube channel. This helped in establishing the branding and presence even more. The channel includes:

- Webinar videos (example [1st webinar](#)).
- IPL [playlists](#).
- Instruction videos (example [Quagga](#)).
- GRAPHIA Researchers [playlist](#).
- End of year messages (example [2025](#)).

More videos will be added during the project's duration. Future videos will continue to include the results of workshops, webinars, and other events, captured and disseminated to amplify the outreach. The full list of GRAPHIA YouTube videos can be found in Appendix table *7.3 GRAPHIA Videos*. The total number of video views as of 16th June is 1425.

2.3 Events

To maximise the dissemination of project results as well as raise awareness, project partners have and will continue to:

- Organise GRAPHIA events such as webinars, workshops, trainings, the final event and similar - Each WP has and will continue to lead and coordinate its own workshops, webinars and trainings with the support of WP6 to disseminate the announcements, findings and outputs.
- Participate in 3rd-party events with presentations, posters or other formats - WPs have been and will continue to be supported by WP6 where necessary to disseminate the findings and outputs.

The events that took place so far have been in-person or online, and where possible, have a hybrid model to allow for the participation of available participants from different regional areas. More details are provided in the following three sections (*Webinars, Workshops, 3rd Party Events*).

Webinars

A total of four webinars targeting a broad audience of potential users — including researchers, librarians, publishers, and industry representatives — were conducted so far. The first webinar, held on 13 June 2025, was an introductory session entitled [*Introduction to Knowledge Graphs*](#), led by GRAPHIA Technical Coordinator Julien Homo. The event was highly successful, with 108 registered participants.

Following this positive response, a new series of three webinars was launched in January 2026, focusing on the utility of knowledge graphs and the technologies underpinning them. This series was designed to further support the onboarding of a wide community of users. The first session in the series, held on 19 February and presented by Julien Homo, showcased concrete use cases under the title [*Why a Knowledge Graph for SSH? Concrete Use Cases with GRAPHIA*](#). The webinar attracted significant interest, with 194 registrations.

The series continued on 19 March 2026 with a presentation by Matteo Romanello (Odoma) entitled [*An Introduction to Large Language Models through GRAPHIA*](#), exploring the role of large language models in the context of the project (158 registered).

The final webinar, held on 16 April 2026 and also delivered by Matteo Romanello, was titled [*Beyond SPARQL: Towards Conversation-Based Access to Knowledge Graphs in GRAPHIA*](#), and focused on innovative approaches to interacting with knowledge graphs (129 registered).

Each webinar was recorded, uploaded to the GRAPHIA YouTube channel and the PowerPoint Presentations (PPTs) files were published in Zenodo. They were also disseminated through social media campaigns and mailing lists (internal and external - more on this strategy in section *2.6 Mailing Lists and Other Channels*).

User Co-Design Workshops

The following six workshops were conducted as part of the GRAPHIA co-design activities to gather user perspectives that inform the development of the GRAPHIA platform.

- *Workshop 1: Knowledge Graph Exploration & Visualisation*

In person: GRAPHIA IPL (October 2025) & Abertay University (November 2025)

Organiser: Abertay University

This in-person workshop was conducted during the GRAPHIA IPL and repeated on the Abertay University campus. These locations were selected to capture a broader participant pool by collecting perspectives from both internal project partners at the IPL and prospective users at Abertay University.

The workshop explored user-driven interface concepts for the interactive exploration and visualisation of the SSH Knowledge Graph. Participants were asked to share their understanding and familiarity with knowledge graphs and to produce physical sketches of features they would expect to see in a knowledge graph interface.

The aim of this workshop was to produce a prioritised set of features to guide early Graphical User Interface (GUI) prototypes for the GRAPHIA Dashboards. In alignment with GRAPHIA technical partners, Knowledge Graph Exploration & Visualisation functionality was selected as the starting point for the co-design workshop series.

The pool of participants for the IPL workshop was from the 125 registered and the Abertay workshop secured 10 registrants.

- *Workshop 2: Advanced Search & Discovery*

Online (February 2026)

Organiser: Abertay University

This online workshop was conducted in connection with the GRAPHIA webinar *Why a Knowledge Graph for SSH? Concrete Use Cases with GRAPHIA* mentioned in the Webinars section. The registrants of the webinar were given the option to also register for the workshop in the same form. This secured 10 registrants. The workshop collected user expectations and needs relating to search features that support research workflows. It also gathered participant feedback on the connected webinar.

The aims for this workshop were as follows:

- Produce a prioritised list of features to guide early GUI prototypes for the GRAPHIA Dashboards.
- Explore participants' understanding of the webinar materials to inform future webinar development.

Participants were encouraged to reflect on the tools they currently use to support their research and to prioritise proposed search features accordingly.

In alignment with GRAPHIA technical partners, Advanced Search & Discovery functionality was selected as the focus of this workshop.

- *Workshop 3: Ethical AI and Responsible Research Practices*

Online (March 2026)

Organiser: Abertay University

This online workshop was conducted in connection with the GRAPHIA webinar *An Introduction to Large Language Models through GRAPHIA*. The registrants of the webinar were given the option to also register for the workshop in the same form. This secured 11 registrants.

The workshop explored user understanding, current practices, and needs relating to the ethical and responsible use of AI in research. It also gathered participant feedback on the connected webinar.

The aims of this workshop were as follows:

- Propose a prioritised list of features to guide early GUI prototypes for the GRAPHIA Dashboards.
- Explore participants' understanding of the webinar materials to inform future webinar development.

Participants were asked to reflect on their understanding of ethical and responsible AI use in research, describe how they currently use AI in their research activities, and discuss the approaches they use to ensure ethical and responsible practice.

In alignment with GRAPHIA technical partners, Ethical AI and Responsible Research Practices functionality was selected as the focus of this workshop.

- *Workshop 4: AI Tools for Organising and Analysing Research Data*

Online (April 2026)

Organiser: Abertay University

This online workshop was conducted in connection with the GRAPHIA webinar *Beyond SPARQL: Towards Conversational Access of Knowledge Graphs*. The registrants of the webinar were given the option to also register for the workshop in the same form. This secured 10 registrants.

The workshop explored user expectations and understanding of AI powered research tools aimed at supporting researcher workflow. It also gathered participant feedback on the connected webinar.

The aims of this workshop were as follows:

- Propose a prioritised list of features to guide research tool prototypes for the GRAPHIA Dashboards.
- Explore participants' understanding of the webinar materials to inform future webinar development.

Participants were asked to describe how they would use AI powered research tools in their research, as well as what outputs they would expect when querying the GRAPHIA knowledge graph.

In alignment with GRAPHIA technical partners, Data Enrichment and Analysis Tools functionality was selected as the focus of this workshop.

- *Workshop 5: Impact Measurement Tool (IMeTo) – warsztat współtworzenia narzędzia do wspierania procesu ewaluacji (workshop run in Polish)*

In person: Poznań, PCSS headquarters (June 2026)

Organisers: PCSS and IBL PAN

Registrants: 9

The aim of the workshop was to collaboratively develop directions for the further design of the IMeTo tool, which is intended to support research evaluation in Poland, particularly in assessing the societal and economic impact of scientific research. The main target audience were librarians, research assessment specialists and researchers.

During the workshop, participants examined the practical aspects of producing “impact cases” – from data collection, through to final reporting. Current challenges related to the time-consuming nature of research evaluation were also addressed, alongside the potential of artificial intelligence to streamline these processes.

The workshop followed a co-creation and design thinking approach, and its outcomes will inform the further development of the IMeTo concept and its functionalities.

- *Workshop 6: Testing GRAPHIA’s Quagga Agent for Exploring the GESIS Knowledge Graph*

Online (June 2026)

Organiser: Abertay University, Odoma, GESIS

This online workshop was conducted in connection with the GRAPHIA Quagga Agent and secured 40 registrants.

The aims of this workshop were as follows:

- Explore the GESIS knowledge graph through the Quagga agent using participants own research questions
- Identify strengths, gaps, and points of friction in the interaction
- Co-design improvements with the development team, focusing on vocabulary alignment, scope, and answer legibility

During this workshop, participants experimented with the Quagga agent to explore the [GESIS Knowledge Graph](#), a knowledge graph focused on social science publications that interlinks the metadata of datasets, publications, variables, survey instruments, authors, and social science concepts drawn from [GESIS Search](#). It is a uniquely rich resource – but querying it traditionally requires Open Standard semantic query language and protocol (SPARQL), a barrier that excludes many researchers from its full potential.

- IPL 2025 workshops and events

A full overview of the IPL is provided in the section *3.8 Progress on Engagement through Innovation Prototyping Labs* and the separate [report](#). The total GRAPHIA related workshops and events held during the event were nine, there were 125 registrants (in person and online).

Internal Workshops

In addition to the externally facing workshops, the GRAPHIA project organised internally facing workshops for a variety of reasons:

- To keep the consortium up to date on the progress.
- To discuss relevant aspects and approaches such as the federation concept.
- To collect feedback and create awareness across all WPs as well as to keep the partners engaged.

These workshops were not counted towards the KPI but are relevant to mention given their importance. One such two-hour workshop was held on the 12th of May online and organised by Foxcub. The focus was on presenting the GRAPHIA federation approach (also accompanied by the publication of a relevant [blog post](#)) where the

knowledge graphs the project is working with were given space and time to voice their progress and questions.

3rd Party Events

As part of the communication, dissemination and engagement strategy, project partners have attended and participated in 25 3rd party events, mostly during conferences or as part of external working groups.

A full list of the events is provided in the Appendix table *7.4 GRAPHIA 3rd Party Events*. They span from publicly held events such as workshops we organised as part of conferences, presentations using PowerPoint slides, poster sessions etc; to specific stakeholders focused closed meetings, working group sessions and workshops.

2.4 Cross-Project Collaboration

To foster collaboration, increase exploitation and communication outreach, GRAPHIA has collaborated with other projects to achieve alignment and increase the effect of its effort. This is reflected in:

- Three multi-day Innovation Prototyping Labs currently held in collaboration with the [LUMEN](#) project. The first such event took place [1-3 Oct 2025](#) in Zagreb, Croatia - more details are provided in Section 3.8.
- Development of [personas](#) as part of WP5 work and in collaboration with the LUMEN project (design, data collection, dissemination campaign alignment).
- A dedicated Mattermost channel for the communication leads on LUMEN and GRAPHIA to stay up to date and facilitate further alignment.

Other projects have also been contacted to discuss potential collaboration and alignment, such as (but not limited to) [FASCA](#) and [ATRIUM](#).

A new collaboration was established between GRAPHIA's WP4 and the [Pelagios Network \(PN\)](#), a global community of practice and bottom-up infrastructure developing the ways and means of linking heritage data online. Project partner Odoma was invited to take over the coordination of PN's Registry working group, together with a representative from Archaeology Data Service as a junior coordinator. This collaboration aims at creating a synergy between PN and GRAPHIA in the context of the GRAPHIA-led effort of gathering data for the [Quagga](#)

benchmark. This synergy and collaboration can have a double outcome: contributing to the Quagga data collection, as well as making known the activities of the GRAPHIA project.

A collaboration was initiated with the Artificial Intelligence for Libraries, Archives & Museums (AI4LAM) group with an initial event organised together in April 2026, joining their mailing list where GRAPHIA shares relevant news as well as investigating other ways of potential collaboration.

2.5 Open Calls for Participation

As part of the dissemination and engagement strategy, different calls for participation were launched, particularly focusing on surveys and calls for pilots. Additionally a very elaborated external mailing lists strategy have been implemented.

2.5.1 Surveys

A short user survey was conducted to support early design considerations for GRAPHIA's planned natural language prompt interface (large language models (LLMs)-supported querying, developed in WP4 by Odoma). The activity complemented ongoing technical work by engaging prospective users and maintaining a feedback loop during development to capture their input.

The survey aimed to:

- Gather end-user needs and expectations for an LLM-based natural language query mechanism.
- Gauge familiarity and comfort with LLM-mediated querying of digital research tools.
- Generate input to support user-centred design recommendations.

The logistics were as follows:

- **Timeframe:** open from mid-November 2025 to mid-January 2026.
- **Audience:** researchers likely to use GRAPHIA at launch, primarily in SSH (not exclusive).
- **Method:** online questionnaire via Google Forms.
- **Participation:** voluntary.

- **Ethics and data governance:** approved by the Abertay University Ethics Committee; anonymous and GDPR-compliant.

Results:

- 46 responses.
- Disciplines covered by the responses: Wide range of SSH backgrounds (eg. Psychology and History), as well as smaller groups including Information and Library Sciences and Computational Sciences.
- Career stages of the respondents: Respondents ranged from early career researchers to specialists. The majority were experienced researchers, with over half occupying established academic or senior research positions.
- Digital familiarity and comfort: Responses ranged from very confident to completely unfamiliar with using digital tools for data analysis, indicating that user technical experience and comfort should not be assumed.

Depending on the project's needs, further surveys will be launched to support the developments.

2.5.2 Call for Pilots

From the 5th of February until the 5th of March 2026, a call for pilots was published that invited commercial organisations working in the ERA with SSH to express their interest in providing use cases for the project. With this call, we collected 23 responses that converted into eight use cases published (in addition to the four resulting from the IPL and the Task 3.3 work in 2025). Some of the other organisations that answered the call for pilots requested more time to internally align and their use cases will probably be published later on in the project.

In this first phase, we are looking to work with organisations that want to test how this emerging infrastructure could be applied in **practical, commercial, or applied contexts**.

Who is this for?

We welcome expressions of interest from a wide range of organisations, based in the European Research Area, including but not limited to:

- Scholarly and trade publishers
- EdTech and research infrastructure providers
- Data providers and aggregators
- SMEs, start-ups, and consultancies working with SSH data
- Any organisation exploring data-driven or AI-supported SSH services

If your work involves **SSH content, data, or audiences**, GRAPHIA may be relevant to you.

Figure 5: Call for pilots

The page contained a Google Form that the organisations filled in to provide their details and use cases suggestions. The use cases collected through the form fed into the Industry Hub mentioned in section 2.1.7 Website.

The next step in this process was to organise two workshops in April 2026 with the organisations that applied and qualified as a use case for this purpose (i.e. they are commercial or private in nature or if they are not commercial, they have a commercial activity they wish to explore/upgrade/investigate through potential collaboration with the GRAPHIA project). Not all opted to join the workshops, some preferred individual conversations or the exchange of information via email.

2.5.2.1 Industrial Use Cases Workshop 1 (22nd April) report

Number of participants: 7 use cases

Type of Organisations Participating

The workshop brought together a diverse group of organisations operating primarily within the scholarly communication, publishing, and data services ecosystem. These included:

- Academic and Open Access publishers.
- Media and content providers.
- Technology and data-driven small to medium enterprises (SMEs).

This composition ensured representation from both content holders and technology-oriented organisations, enabling a balanced perspective on data production, management, and exploitation.

Rationale for Participation

Organisations for the first workshop were selected based on the following criteria:

- Active role in managing structured and semi-structured SSH data.
- Existing or emerging engagement with metadata standards and publishing workflows.
- Demonstrated interest in AI-driven services, including semantic search, recommendation systems, and knowledge graph applications.
- Capacity and willingness to contribute real-world datasets and pilot use cases.

This combined approach ensured that participants were not only representative of the target ecosystem, but also motivated and relevant for co-creation activities. Their participation aligns with GRAPHIA's objective to co-develop solutions with stakeholders who are both technically capable and strategically positioned to benefit from knowledge graph integration, while also reflecting varying levels of organisational and technical maturity.

Focus of the Discussions

The workshop discussions were structured around four main thematic axes:

- *Data Infrastructure & Interoperability*
Understanding current data environments, formats, and metadata practices revealed a high degree of heterogeneity, with multiple standards (e.g. Dublin Core, ONIX, MARC21, TEI) used in parallel. This confirmed both sector maturity and fragmentation, highlighting interoperability as a central challenge.
- *Technical Readiness & Integration Capacity*
Participants demonstrated strong technical readiness, particularly in relation to structured data and Application Programming Interface (API) usage. However, this readiness is not fully reflected in data exposure and interoperability practices, as only part of the participants currently make their data externally accessible. This points to a gap between internal capability and external integration.

AI Services & Innovation Potential

Discussions highlighted a strong interest not only in stable services but also in experimentation and innovation. Priority areas included:

- Semantic search.
- Entity linking.
- Content enrichment.

This indicates that participants are seeking both operational tools and exploratory environments for developing new AI-driven services.

Use Case Co-Design

A key focus was the definition of practical, outcome-oriented pilot use cases, with strong interest in:

- Metadata enrichment.
- Knowledge graph integration.

- Automated classification.
- Domain-specific datasets (e.g. publishing, education, agriculture).

Participants clearly prioritised tangible results and real-world applicability over purely conceptual approaches.

2.5.2.2 Industrial Use Cases Workshop 2 (29th April) report

Number of participants: 3 use cases

Type of Organisations Participating

The workshop brought together a small but diverse group of organisations operating within the scholarly communication, publishing, and media ecosystem. These included:

- Academic and specialised publishers.
- Research dissemination platforms and journals.
- Media and content providers.

Although limited in number, the participants represent content-driven organisations with established roles in producing, curating, and disseminating scholarly and informational material. Compared to the first workshop, the composition leans more strongly toward content holders rather than technology-oriented organisations.

Rationale for Participation

Organisations for the second workshop were selected based on the following criteria:

- Active role in content production and dissemination within the SSH domain.
- Use or management of metadata, even at a basic or intermediate level.
- Interest in improving visibility, discoverability, and content accessibility.
- Willingness to explore practical pilot use cases.

This approach ensured participation from organisations that are directly involved in content creation and dissemination, while also reflecting varying levels of technical maturity. Their participation aligns with GRAPHIA's objective to engage content holders who can benefit from knowledge graph integration, particularly in enhancing discoverability, linking content, and increasing the reach of their publications.

Focus of the Discussions

The workshop discussions were structured around four main thematic axes:

- *Data Infrastructure & Interoperability*

Participants reported a heterogeneous content landscape, including journals, books, bibliographic databases, encyclopedias, and full-text repositories. Content is often multilingual, spanning English, Spanish, and other European and classical languages.

While metadata is used across all participating organisations, its level of structure varies from basic to well-structured. This indicates the presence of foundational practices, but also highlights inconsistencies in standardisation and interoperability readiness.

- *Technical Readiness & Integration Capacity*

Compared to the first workshop, this group demonstrates a lower level of technical orientation. While metadata practices are in place, there is limited evidence of systematic data exposure or integration mechanisms (e.g., APIs, interoperability frameworks).

This suggests that technical capacity exists at a basic level but is not yet strategically developed for integration within broader data ecosystems.

AI Services & Innovation Potential

Unlike the first group, interest in AI-driven services was less explicitly articulated. Instead, participants expressed a more practical and immediate focus on improving:

- Searchability.
- Content visibility.
- User engagement.
- Linking between content.

This indicates a shift from innovation-driven objectives toward operational improvements, reflecting the needs of content-focused organisations.

Use Case Co-Design

Discussions highlighted a strong preference for practical, hands-on engagement. The most prominent proposed use case was “A hands-on pilot session to explore and experiment with the GRAPHIA system”.

This reflects a need for experiential learning and guided interaction, rather than abstract or highly technical pilot definitions.

Cross-Cutting Insights from the Discussion Across Both Workshops

Across all thematic areas, several transversal findings emerged:

- Resource constraints (human, technical, time-related) were identified as the primary barrier, outweighing legal or purely technical challenges.
- Metadata fragmentation reinforces the need for mapping, harmonisation, and crosswalk mechanisms within GRAPHIA.
- Bottlenecks are increasingly organisational rather than technical, including policy gaps, governance issues, and inter-institutional coordination.
- There is a clear need for solutions that emphasise:
 - Ease of integration.
 - Automation.
 - Low-overhead onboarding.
 - Visibility and discoverability.
 - Content diversity and multilingualism.
 - Limited indexing in broader ecosystems.
 - Platform isolation.
 - Ease of use and accessibility.

Overall, the discussion evolved from technical mapping of current capacities to a more strategic and application-oriented dialogue, with a strong emphasis on feasible implementation pathways and co-designed pilots.

General Observations Across Both Workshops

- All participants remained engaged throughout the full duration of the workshop, demonstrating strong interest and commitment.
- The discussion around participants' needs was particularly dynamic, enabling a deeper understanding and refinement of requirements, as well as initial reflections on how these could be addressed within the GRAPHIA framework.
- The interactive format—posing questions followed by immediate clarification and short discussions—proved highly effective. Compared to a consolidated Q&A session at the end, this approach facilitated more direct, precise, and actionable feedback.
- Participation levels were lower in the second workshop. This may be partially attributed to language-related factors, as a significant proportion of invited stakeholders originate from Spain. While the session was conducted in English, this may have influenced the level of active engagement. At the same time, additional factors should also be considered. Further investigation is

recommended to better understand and address these dynamics in future sessions.

Tools Used to Collect Feedback Across Both Workshops

A combination of interactive and qualitative tools was used to ensure comprehensive feedback collection:

- Live polling tool (Mentimeter) for structured questionnaire responses.
- Guided discussion prompts to capture qualitative insights.
- Open-ended responses during the session for deeper contextual understanding.
- Real-time clarification and moderation to refine answers and ensure consistency.

This hybrid approach enabled both quantitative aggregation and rich qualitative input, enhancing the reliability and usability of the findings.

Next Steps After Both Workshops

Following the workshops, participants were invited to proceed with the next phase of engagement, focusing on the definition and refinement of concrete use cases within the GRAPHIA framework.

- **Use Case Description Submission:** Participants were requested to access the dedicated document and provide a high-level description of their proposed use case(s) within the GRAPHIA project. This initial input formed the basis for further discussion and development.
- **Integration into the Industry Hub:** The submitted use cases are featured in the GRAPHIA Industry Hub, launched in June. Participants were encouraged to submit multiple use cases if relevant.
- **Internal Review and Follow-Up:** All submitted use cases will be reviewed internally by the GRAPHIA team to assess their scope, requirements, and alignment with the project's technical capabilities.

This process will support:

- The identification of appropriate points of contact within the consortium.
- The alignment of use cases with ongoing technical developments.

2.6 Mailing Lists and Other Channels

Through the first months, it was challenging to gain enough attention and create enough engagement just through the established channels and project partners. At the end of 2025, a special effort was made to create a matrix that collected external, mailing lists, Slack channels, newsletters, and similar channels where news could be promoted to make sure a greater number of stakeholders is being engaged and contacted. The focus was to find online SSH hubs of researchers, industry, not for profit organisations, knowledge graph enthusiasts and similar stakeholders. This was proven to be very effective: as an example is the survey mentioned in the section 2.5 *Open Calls for Participation*. At launch, it only received three responses, however after sharing it in all the channels found as part of the research for hubs, it received 43 additional responses over three weeks during December. Another example is the GRAPHIA mailing list which had approximately 100 subscribers in Q3 2025, while it reached almost 400 in June 2026.

We believe that, while this success is a result of a variety of factors, the external dissemination strategy through the matrix contributed greatly to these results. The matrix is a living list, new channels are being added as they are discovered, and their effectiveness is being monitored to understand how active they are in providing results.

Some of the used channels are:

- Google Groups such as AI4LAM and Nanopublications.
- Slack channels dedicated to the Knowledge Graph Conference and DataTalks
- Mailing lists that have a global reach (example IFLA), a specific research domain (example the Linguist) or a university hub (example University of Bern).
- External newsletter such as the LIBER insider.

Examples of messaging through those channels can be seen below.

Figure 6. Webinar announcement in a Slack channel

EVENT | Webinar: An Introduction to Large Language Models through GRAPHIA

This webinar offers an accessible introduction to how large language models (LLMs) work—and what they can (and cannot) do for research in the social sciences and humanities. Using GRAPHIA as a case study, the session walks participants through the lifecycle of an LLM, from pre-training to domain adaptation, while introducing core concepts such as tokenisation, embeddings, transformer architecture, and prompting. Date & time: **19 March at 2 PM CET**. [Register here](#).

Figure 7. Webinar announcement in LIBER Insider

LINGUIST List 37.494

Thu Feb 05 2026

FYI: GRAPHIA Invites Linguists to Provide Research Questions

Editor for this issue: Daniel Swanson <daniel@linguistlist.org>

Date: 05-Feb-2026
From: Ursula Rabar <ursula.rabar@operas-eu.org>
Subject: GRAPHIA Invites Linguists to Provide Research Questions
[✉ E-mail this message to a friend](#)

As part of GRAPHIA, a European research project working to make Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) data easier to discover, connect, and reuse through a shared knowledge graph, we are looking for your suggestions.

We believe that for linguistics researchers, this work is especially relevant. Linguistic data—corpora, lexicons, annotations, grammars, language resources, and metadata—often exists in rich but siloed forms across projects and infrastructures. Knowledge graphs provide a way to connect these resources across languages, domains, and methodologies, enabling new forms of discovery, comparison, and reuse.

Figure 8. Call for query questions in the Linguist

3. Exploitation

The GRAPHIA exploitation strategy is structured to maximise the impact and uptake of the project's KERs both during and beyond the lifetime of the project. Exploitation planning is led under Task 6.1 – Innovation Management and Exploitation, in coordination with the partners responsible for developing each KER, and is extended into industry outreach and commercialisation pathways under Task 6.3. This work builds upon commitments made in the GA and Description of Action (DoA) and is guided by the overarching ambition to support sustainable, open and interoperable research infrastructure in SSH.

3.1 Objectives

The exploitation activities in GRAPHIA aim to:

- Support the integration of project outputs into EOSC and SSHOC ecosystems.
- Promote the reuse, uptake, and integration of GRAPHIA results by both academic and non-academic actors.
- Prepare for the sustainability of selected outputs beyond the project's funding period, particularly the SSH Knowledge Graph.

- Coordinate the definition, protection and licensing of intellectual property arising from the project.
- Align with the [Horizon Results Platform \(HRP\)](#) template to ensure consistent documentation and visibility of exploitable results.

Industry outreach and routes to commercialisation are addressed under Task 6.3 and reported in Section 3.7. Task 6.1 and Task 6.3 are jointly chaired by Industry Commons Foundation (ICF) and co-reported through a shared monthly rolling minutes process.

3.2 Key Exploitable Results at a Glance

GRAPHIA has seven KERs, each with a named champion responsible for evolving its expanded definition, exploitation strategy, Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) approach and dissemination actions through the KER Champions process under Task 6.1. The seventh, Quagga (KER7), is an unexpected key exploitable result, with exploitation outputs delivered in the first half of the project and beyond the six KERs originally defined in the proposal. The table below provides a compact reference view. Detailed per-KER strategies are set out in Section 3.3.

- **KER1: SSH Knowledge Graph.** A cornerstone outcome of the project: an advanced Knowledge Graph for SSH that combines established technologies in a hybrid architecture, integrating data from various sources and enhancing data findability, understanding and decision-making.
- **KER2: LLM4SSH.** An LLM tailored for SSH that provides domain-specific insights and analytics at high performance and lower cost, deployable on private servers for increased data privacy.
- **KER3: Catalogue for Next-Generation Technological Instruments and Data Lifecycle Management Workflows for SSH** (previously named ‘Prototypes for Next-Generation SSH Instruments’). State-of-the-art prototypes incorporating advanced data acquisition and processing technologies, enabling interactive digital twins and in-depth analysis of SSH cultural objects and digital data.
- **KER4: SSH Citations Index.** A software framework for the automatic extraction, indexation, enrichment and use of citation data from any SSH resource, increasing the visibility and tracking of research inputs and outputs.
- **KER5: Technical Interoperability Framework: Toolkits, Workflows, APIs.** A structured set of guidelines, protocols and interfaces ensuring seamless

integration and consistent communication across systems, tools and services in SSH and beyond, aligned with FAIR principles.

- **KER6: Real-World Use Case Implementations.** A series of concrete academic and commercial use cases, each selected for its exploitation potential and developed with an individual exploitation plan.
- **KER7: Quagga.** An ecosystem of data and tools for LLM-based question answering over SSH knowledge graphs, providing conversational natural-language access to the GRAPHIA federated Knowledge Graph and lowering the technical barrier to its exploration.

KER	Title	Lead WP	Champion	Primary User Groups	Licence / Protection
KER1	SSH Knowledge Graph	WP2	Julien Homo (Foxcub/CNRS)	Researchers, infrastructure providers, libraries	Joint Ownership Agreement and Policy
KER2	LLM4SSH	WP4	Matteo Romanello (Odoma)	SSH researchers, public bodies, cultural institutions, industry	Open source (MIT)
KER3	Catalogue for Next-Generation Technological Instruments and Data Lifecycle Management Workflows for SSH	WP3	Giovanni Pescarmona (MiC)	Research infrastructures, RI providers, industry	Joint Ownership + commercial as applicable
KER4	SSH Citations Index	WP4	Matteo Romanello (Odoma)	Researchers, publishers, data and service providers	Open source (MIT)
KER5	Technical Interoperability	WP2, WP3	Yann Le Franc (eSDF)	Infrastructure and data	Open source (MIT)

	Framework			providers, developers	
KER6	Real-World Use Case Implementations	WP3, WP4	Michela Magas (ICF)	Broad, context-depe ndent	Per use case
KER7	Quagga	WP4, WP6	Matteo Romanello (Odoma)	SSH researchers, knowledge graph users	Component ownership; licence to be confirmed

Table 5. GRAPHIA KERs at a glance

3.3 Per-KER Exploitation Strategy

Detailed per-KER planning is maintained in the GRAPHIA KER Champions Working Document under Task 6.1. That document serves as the source for HRP entries. The summaries below capture the exploitation direction for each KER at Month 18.

3.3.1 KER1 – SSH Knowledge Graph

Champion. Julien Homo (Foxcub/CNRS), supported by Yann Le Franc (eSDF) and Tiziana Tiradritti (Net7).

Description. A federated SSH Knowledge Graph connecting autonomous graphs (GoTriple knowledge graph, OpenCitations, ORKG, GESIS, EHRI, E-RIHS) through the GRAPHIA Ontology and Scientific Knowledge Graph – Interoperability Framework (SKG-IF). GoTriple knowledge graph is the project-maintained core service, extending GoTriple metadata with AI- and Natural Language Processing (NLP)-derived enrichments.

Exploitation route. SPARQL endpoints and Resource Description Framework (RDF) dumps; SKG-IF API and Federated Gateway; a GRAPHIA web interface co-designed with end-users; integration with EOSC and the SSHOC. Industry engagement via the Call for Pilots and the Industry Use Cases Digital Hub.

IPR approach. Consortium joint ownership under a Joint Ownership Agreement; permissive open-source software licence (MIT foreseen); CC BY 4.0 default for enriched metadata.

Early adopters. Infobip, Metaphacts and MTF Labs (Open Minds) onboarding; additional leads from the Call for Pilots cohort.

3.3.2 KER2 – LLM4SSH

Champion. Matteo Romanello (Odoma), supported by ICF (Michela Magas, Polina Proutskova).

Description. A domain-adapted LLM tailored to SSH, combining a generative model for conversation with encoder-based foundational models for textual embeddings.

Exploitation route. Released openly to the SSH community as a dataset dump or via API; institutional Git hosting, containerised deployments, and listing in the SSHOC and other EOSC-aligned catalogues.

IPR approach. MIT licence for model software and code; CC BY 4.0 for released training resources where rights permit.

Early adopters. SSH research groups, cultural institutions, scholarly publishers, and industry actors engaged through the Call for Pilots.

3.3.3 KER3 – Catalogue for Next-Generation Technological Instruments and Data Lifecycle Management Workflows for SSH

Champion. Giovanni Pescarmona (MiC), supported by Marcin Plociennik (PSNC).

Description. This KER is a set of advanced hardware and software tools and workflows contributed by GRAPHIA partners and relevant to SSH data lifecycle management, spanning from acquisition and processing to enrichment, interpretation, and publication. The instruments, tools and workflows are captured in a structured catalogue implemented through the SSHOC and support the generation and management of multimodal data across a wide range of SSH and heritage science domains. The catalogue includes both physical instruments, such as environmental sensors and multi-sensor 3D scanning platforms, and digital services, such as annotation environments, citation extraction and classification tools, data aggregation pipelines, transcription platforms, and knowledge graph infrastructures.

Exploitation route. Delivered via E-RIHS research facilities and the SSHOC; commercial upscaling pursued with industry where applicable.

IPR approach. Consortium Joint Ownership Agreements and IPR Policies; commercial exploitation paths per instrument.

Early adopters. E-RIHS consortium members and industry actors engaged through T6.3.

3.3.4 KER4 – SSH Citations Index

Champion. Matteo Romanello (Odoma), supported by ICF (Polina Proutskova, Michela Magas).

Description. A framework of AI models and training data for extracting, indexing and enriching citation data from SSH literature, wrapped as reusable containerised modules.

Exploitation route. Released as an open, documented framework with tutorials; drives a systematic effort to expand SSH citation data coverage.

IPR approach. MIT licence for framework software; extracted citation data released under open licences where rights permit.

Early adopters. Researchers, publishers, data and service providers across the scholarly publishing and digital humanities communities.

3.3.5 KER5 – Technical Interoperability Framework: Toolkits, Workflows, APIs

Champion. Yann Le Franc (eSDF), supported by Julien Homo (Foxcub/CNRS) and Tiziana Tiradritti (Net7).

Description. Standardised toolkits, workflows and APIs enabling cross-infrastructure collaboration, aligned with FAIR principles and integrated with EOSC services. A first good-practice workflow, “Using GoTriple data for your SSH data science tasks”, is published on the SSH Open Marketplace with the ATRIUM project.

Exploitation route. Institutional Git hosting; listing in the SSHOC and EOSC-aligned catalogues; community-driven contribution.

IPR approach. MIT licence.

Early adopters. Infrastructure and data providers, and tool developers across SSH research infrastructures.

3.3.6 KER6 – Real-World Use Case Implementations

Champion. Michela Magas (ICF), supported by Valeria Ciocan (Odoma).

Description. Use cases demonstrating the added value of the SSH Knowledge Graph and associated instruments. Eight, including both industry and academia, were identified at the time of writing the project proposal (EHRI, CNRS MAP, Cyprus institute, CNR, GGP and GESIS, Genius Loci, Resilience and OAEBUDT). These will be

described and published as part of a report due M36. Through the 2025 IPL (October 2025) and the Call for Pilots (closed 5 March 2026), 12 further viable commercial SSH use cases were published as part of the Industry Hub.

Exploitation route. Individual business models per use case, consolidated through the Task 6.3 portfolio-of-business-models approach (see Section 3.7).

IPR approach. Protection models vary per use case, determined by the consortium members of each use case.

Early adopters. Early industry engagement with Infobip and Metaphacts; broader adopter set to be documented in deliverable 6.4 following pilot workshops.

3.3.7 KER7 – Quagga

Champion. Matteo Romanello (Odoma), supported by Polina Proutskova (ICF).

Description. Quagga is GRAPHIA's ecosystem of data and tools for LLM-based knowledge graph question answering. It comprises three components: the Quagga benchmark, a community-crowdsourced evaluation resource pairing natural-language questions with SPARQL queries across SSH knowledge graphs; the Quagga agent, an agentic system built on open-weight LLMs that gives conversational access to those graphs through retrieval-augmented generation; and Explore Your Graphs Engine (EXYGEN), an API that generates the knowledge-graph metadata grounding query generation from any SPARQL endpoint. Its primary application is a natural-language interface to GRAPHIA's federated Knowledge Graph and the GoTriple knowledge graph, lowering the technical barrier to exploring them.

Exploitation route. EXYGEN offered as an API; the Quagga agent accessed through an OpenWebUI interface for users of the Quagga benchmark; fine-tuned text-to-SPARQL models and the benchmark dataset released on the Hugging Face Hub. Odoma is developing the agent into a commercial product, GraphChat.

IPR approach. Component-level ownership by the developing beneficiaries, with software licensing to be confirmed and the crowdsourced benchmark released as open data.

Early adopters. SSH researchers working with knowledge graphs and users of the GRAPHIA federated knowledge graph and GoTriple knowledge graph; commercial route via Odoma's GraphChat.

3.4 Knowledge and IP Management Plan

3.4.1 Introduction

The GRAPHIA project brings together commercial companies, research institutions, and non-profit organisations to advance Knowledge Graphs, AI Services, and Next Generation Instrumentation for R&D in SSH. As with all collaborative Horizon Europe projects, GRAPHIA generates valuable results across its partnership, and enabling the commercial exploitation of those results is a key measure of project success.

This section, produced under Task 6.3 Industry Outreach and Commercialisation, sets out a practical intellectual property (IP) management and exploitation strategy for the GRAPHIA consortium. Its purpose is to provide a clear, principled framework that enables partners to plan for and pursue the commercial exploitation of their results with confidence, while respecting the collaborative spirit of the project and the provisions of the Consortium Agreement.

The strategy draws on an established IP management methodology, the IP Stack model, developed by ICF over the past decade and previously deployed in European Union (EU)-funded Innovation Actions. Applying this model to GRAPHIA's context provides a structured approach to identifying, attributing, and protecting intellectual property at the component level, ensuring that the partners who create exploitable results retain the clarity they need to bring those results to market.

The EC values exploitation as a central outcome of Horizon Europe projects. Investment, job creation, market reach, and long-term sustainability are among the indicators used to assess project impact. This strategy is designed to support those outcomes by removing ambiguity, encouraging early commercial deployment, and providing a framework that gives investors and commercial partners the certainty they require. It complements the work of Task 6.1 (IPLs), which provides the collaborative environment for creating new innovation layers, and should be read alongside the project's broader exploitation activities.

3.4.2 Principles

Four guiding principles underpin the IP management approach proposed in this document. They are intended to be practical, fair, and consistent with the spirit of the

Consortium Agreement and the Commission's expectations for Horizon Europe projects.

First, ownership follows authorship. Where a partner has solely developed a result using its own personnel and resources, that partner is the sole owner. This is consistent with Clause 8.1 of the Consortium Agreement and reflects a straightforward application of the principle that results belong to the party that generates them. Sole development is evidenced by repository ownership, commit histories, and the absence of external code contributions.

Second, ownership is assessed per unit of result, not per suite of tools. A platform may comprise multiple discrete components, each with its own development history and authorship. Ownership is determined at the level of the individual component, not at the level of the integrated system. This granularity is essential for clarity.

Third, exploitation should be enabled, not impeded. The purpose of an exploitation strategy is to get results to market. Ambiguity in IP ownership deters investment and delays commercialisation. This strategy seeks to resolve such ambiguity proactively, so that partners can engage investors and pursue market opportunities without uncertainty.

Fourth, transparency over litigation. Partners are encouraged to declare their exploitation intentions early and to document their development activities openly. Where arrangements are structured transparently, conflicts are prevented rather than resolved after the fact. This benefits the entire consortium.

3.4.3 Context

GRAPHIA's consortium includes partners with diverse objectives and motivations. Some are primarily research-oriented, contributing to the advancement of knowledge in their fields. Others are commercial entities for whom the project represents an opportunity to develop tools and services with direct market application. Still others occupy a bridging role, facilitating innovation and translation between research and industry. This diversity is a strength of the consortium, but it also means that partners approach IP ownership and exploitation from different perspectives.

The standard provisions of the Consortium Agreement, drawn from the EC's model, provide a robust foundation for IP management. Clause 8.1 establishes that results are owned by the party that generates them. Clause 8.3 addresses joint ownership where results are generated jointly. Clause 8.3.1 provides that each joint owner is entitled to exploit jointly owned results. These provisions reflect well-established principles of collaborative research governance.

These provisions are clear in principle. In practice, however, collaborative projects that produce software components benefit from a clear interpretation of how these clauses apply to individual tools and services. The challenge is not one of inadequacy in the agreement, but of ensuring that its provisions are applied with sufficient granularity to give commercial partners the certainty they need to attract investment and pursue exploitation. Where a partner has built a discrete tool entirely with its own resources, the pathway to commercialisation should be clear and unambiguous. This strategy offers that interpretation.

3.4.4 The IP Stack Model

The IP Stack is a model for structuring intellectual property within collaborative innovation projects. Developed by ICF over the past decade, it has been refined through practical deployment in EU-funded projects and through the Foundation's IPL methodology.

The model was first formalised in the Horizon 2020 MusicBricks project (Grant Agreement 644871). To incentivise creative developers, the MusicBricks consortium created an entirely new layer of intellectual property that could be deployed across a range of projects and programmes. By adding Innovation IP to the existing Background IP and Research IP, the project enabled partners to take academic research results to market in a way that fairly reflected the development team's creative work. The Consortium Agreement was rewritten to include this new area of Innovation IP, enabling innovators to take ownership of their layer of IP. In one case, the clarity provided by the IP Stack led to a patent search conducted just four months after an innovative seed idea. Partners agreed on licensing structures that supported and encouraged open innovation, predominantly MIT licences, with commercial licences offered under fair and reasonable conditions.

The EC subsequently referenced MusicBricks as best practice in multiple EU contexts, including the CONNECT Advisory Forum (CAF) recommendations for the H2020 Programme 2018 to 2020, the Alliance for Internet of Things Innovation (AIOTI), EU Knowledge Valorisation, and the Open Innovation Strategy and Policy Group (OISPG) newsletter on the Digital Single Market portal. The IP Stack document was made available as a reference for other ecosystem-building Innovation Actions. The model's influence has continued to grow: more recently, CERN requested that the IP Stack model be implemented in its own consortium agreements, recognising its value as a framework for managing IP in large-scale collaborative research.

The model comprises three layers. Background IP is the existing intellectual property that a partner brings into the project. It remains owned by the originating partner and is unaffected by collaborative activities. Research IP is intellectual property developed during the project as an interface or translation layer. Under the standard provisions of Clause 8.1, it is owned by the generating partner. Where a result is genuinely co-developed, contribution shares are documented to reflect each party's actual input. Innovation IP is intellectual property generated through collaborative activities, such as IPLs, on top of the existing layers. It is novel, additive, portable, and separately encapsulated. Crucially, Innovation IP does not erode ownership of the underlying layers. Together, the three layers combine to create a single functional and trackable proposition.

A useful analogy is that of component manufacturing. A Siemens component installed in a Volkswagen vehicle does not become Volkswagen's property by virtue of integration. Each layer in the IP Stack is identifiable, attributable, and separately exploitable. The IP Stacking model securely records and attributes the creation of each layer of IP, providing the provenance and clarity that both partners and investors require.

3.4.5 Unit of Result

Central to this strategy is the concept of the unit of result: the level of granularity at which IP ownership is assessed. Rather than treating an entire platform or toolchain as a single result, the IP Stack model recognises that complex systems are composed of discrete components, each with a distinct development history, authorship, and ownership profile. This distinction is particularly important in software-intensive

projects, where a single integrated service may incorporate contributions from multiple independent development efforts.

A unit of result is a discrete software component, identifiable by one or more of the following characteristics: it occupies a distinct repository or clearly separated module within a larger codebase; it performs a defined function or capability; it has a traceable commit history showing authorship; and it is independently deployable or operates as an independent service. These characteristics provide objective, verifiable criteria for delineating the boundaries of a result.

Ownership of a unit of result is determined by who built it, not by its proximity to other work or by participation in meetings where it was discussed. This is directly consistent with Clause 8.1 of the Consortium Agreement, which provides that results are owned by the party that generates them. Where multiple partners have contributed to a unit of result, the nature and extent of each contribution is documented, and ownership shares reflect actual technical input rather than assumptions based on consortium membership.

Applying this principle ensures that a partner who has developed a component solely using its own personnel and within its own repositories retains unambiguous ownership of that component, regardless of the broader collaborative context in which it was created. Equally, it ensures that genuinely collaborative results are recognised as such, with contributions properly attributed.

3.4.6 Illustrative Application

To illustrate the application of the IP Stack model within GRAPHIA, consider the following scenario. A commercial partner within the consortium has developed a software component, a natural-language-to-query translation engine, exclusively with its own personnel. The development has taken place within private repositories, and the commit history shows contributions solely from the partner's own team. No code contributions from other consortium partners are present in the component's codebase. The partner intends to commercialise this tool during the project or after its conclusion and is actively building an investor base.

Under the IP Stack model, this component is classified as Research IP, solely owned by the developing partner under Clause 8.1. The evidence for sole ownership is clear and

well-documented: a defined function, a distinct repository, traceable authorship, and no external contributions. Adjacent work contributed by other partners, such as synthetic data augmentation, constitutes a separate unit of result with its own ownership profile. The adjacency of the work does not confer shared ownership of the core engine. Each component is assessed independently.

Where future collaborative activities, such as IPLs, generate additional functionality on top of the engine, that output is classified as Innovation IP. It is separately encapsulated and does not alter the ownership of the underlying component. In practice, this means the partner's tool should be positioned as a service layer at IPLs: other participants build on top of it, not into it. This preserves the integrity of the core component while enabling the collaborative innovation that the project requires.

Several recommended practices follow from this classification. The partner should ring-fence its component through versioned releases, establishing a timestamped baseline that documents the tool's state prior to any collaborative extension. An IPL fork strategy should be adopted, maintaining an experimental branch separate from the canonical codebase. Early commercial deployment during the project is strongly encouraged and should be reported as a positive outcome at the Month 18 review, thereby demonstrating the project's economic impact. This strategy provides the clarity that investors require and positions the partner's exploitation activity as a success story for the consortium as a whole.

3.4.7 Interpretation of the Consortium Agreement

This strategy does not propose amendments to the Consortium Agreement or the GA. Rather, it offers a practical interpretation of the existing provisions as they apply to the exploitation of software components developed within the project. The intention is to build constructively on the framework the Commission has established, applying it with the granularity that software development demands.

Clause 8.1 provides that results are owned by the party that generates them. This strategy applies the principle at the level of the individual component, consistent with the unit of result concept described above. Where a partner has developed a component solely with its own personnel and within its own repositories, the application of Clause 8.1 is straightforward: the result belongs to that partner.

Clause 8.3 addresses joint ownership, which applies where results are genuinely co-developed. Co-development, for the purposes of this strategy, is defined by actual technical contribution, evidenced by code commits and documented development activity, rather than by meeting attendance, discussion, or adjacent work on related components. Clause 8.3.1 provides that, where joint ownership applies, each joint owner is entitled to exploit the jointly owned results. This strategy recommends that ownership shares in such cases reflect the actual proportion of each partner's contribution, rather than an automatic equal split.

These interpretations are offered as recommendations to stimulate exploitation, consistent with the Commission's expectations for Horizon Europe projects. They are intended to provide practical clarity, not to narrow any partner's rights.

3.4.8 Recommendations

The following recommendations are offered as best practices for any GRAPHIA partner with results that have potential for commercial exploitation.

- **Partners should document and version their work consistently.** Clear repository structures, commit histories, and release tagging provide an evidence base for ownership claims and give investors confidence in the technology's provenance.
- **Partners should maintain a clear separation between their core IP and any collaborative extensions arising from project activities.** The IPL fork strategy and service-layer positioning described in this document provide practical mechanisms to achieve this.
- **Commercial deployment should begin early, where feasible.** The European Commission views early exploitation as a positive indicator of project impact. Partners should not wait until the conclusion of the project to pursue market opportunities. Early deployment activities should be reported at review milestones as evidence of the project's economic impact.
- **Exploitation strategies should be framed in terms the Commission values: job creation, market reach, sustainability, and contribution to European competitiveness.** This alignment benefits both the exploiting partner and the consortium as a whole.

These recommendations are offered as practical guidance. They do not constitute legal requirements and are not intended to override the provisions of the Consortium Agreement or the Grant Agreement.

3.4.9 Future Considerations

As GRAPHIA's technical services mature throughout the project, the exploitation strategy should be revisited and expanded. The IP Stack model is inherently adaptable and can be applied to result categories beyond software components.

AI-generated enrichments and annotations, for example, represent a growing category of project output whose ownership and exploitation potential will benefit from structured classification. Similarly, data processing innovations and novel methodologies arising from Innovation Prototyping Lab activities may warrant their own exploitation frameworks. As the landscape of AI-assisted research tools evolves, questions of attribution and ownership will only become more salient.

This document establishes the foundational principles. Future iterations will apply them to the broader range of GRAPHIA's outputs as they emerge, ensuring that the consortium's approach to IP management keeps pace with the development of its technical capabilities.

A further area for development concerns the governance of IP as it moves between partners within the consortium. The IP Stack model addresses the question of ownership: who created a result, and to whom does it belong. A complementary question arises when results are shared, integrated, or deployed across organisational boundaries: under what terms does a component travel, and what rights and obligations accompany it? This is the domain of what ICF has termed **Transfer IP** (or “Transferable IP”): the explicit management of intellectual property and usage rights as part of the workflow by which models, code, datasets, or other results move between contributors.

The concept was developed in the context of Trusted Research Environments for Healthcare AI, where the secure sharing of trained models between institutions requires clear, rigorous definitions of ownership, licensing, and permitted use. In a [white paper](#) produced by ICF for the Swedish TRE4HealthAI initiative, Transfer IP is defined as a procedural framework that embeds IP governance directly into the validation and export workflow. Rather than relying on ad hoc arrangements

negotiated after the fact, Transfer IP establishes the rules of the game upfront: template agreements that define who owns a shared result, under what licence it may be used, and what restrictions apply to downstream deployment. This clarity protects data contributors (for instance, by mandating that a model trained on one institution's data may be used only for non-commercial research unless otherwise licensed) and gives researchers confidence in how they can later exploit their work.

Transfer IP is not a layer in the IP Stack; it is a governance mechanism that operates alongside it. Where the IP Stack answers “who owns this?”, Transfer IP answers “on what terms does this move?” The two are complementary. In a consortium of twenty partners sharing knowledge graph components, query tools, and enrichment pipelines, the Transfer IP framework could provide standardised agreements governing how those components are shared, integrated, and reused across the partnership. Future iterations of this strategy should explore applying Transfer IP to GRAPHIA's collaborative workflows, drawing on the template agreements and validation processes developed in the healthcare context and adapting them for the SSH knowledge graph domain.

3.4.10 Conclusion

This strategy is fundamentally about enabling exploitation as a positive outcome of the GRAPHIA project. The IP Stack model provides a proven, practical framework for structuring intellectual property within collaborative innovation projects. It has been validated in previous EU-funded projects, recognised by the European Commission as best practice, and adopted by major research organisations including CERN.

By applying the IP Stack to GRAPHIA, commercial partners can plan their exploitation activities with confidence, knowing that their solely developed results are clearly attributed and protected. Investors see the clarity they need to commit capital. The consortium as a whole benefits from a transparent, principled approach to IP management that aligns with the Commission's expectations for Horizon Europe projects and positions GRAPHIA's results for maximum impact.

3.5 Integration into Existing Ecosystems

A major objective of GRAPHIA's exploitation approach is to ensure that project results are not standalone artefacts, but rather components of a larger, interconnected

research infrastructure landscape. To that end, all KERs are being designed and documented for **interoperability, reusability, and integration**.

Key target ecosystems for integration include:

- **EOSC.** Through metadata alignment, licensing compatibility, and adherence to FAIR principles and generally to the [EOSC handbook](#), GRAPHIA tools, datasets and frameworks will be made discoverable and usable within EOSC environments. EOSC compatibility is being considered from the earliest design stages of all technical outputs.
- **SSHOC.** GRAPHIA prototypes and tools, especially those related to research instrumentation and data processing workflows, are intended for listing and promotion through the SSHOC. This will ensure wide visibility across the SSH research infrastructure community.
- **OPERAS Research Infrastructure.** As the WP6 lead and a core partner, OPERAS will play a central role in anchoring GRAPHIA outputs in existing services and communication channels. This includes support for the continued hosting of digital content, documentation and community engagement activities.
- **Standardisation networks and open-source communities.** Where relevant, tools and services will contribute to ongoing discussions and developments within standardisation bodies and relevant open-source development forums. This includes participation in thematic EOSC Task Forces, LUMEN and ATRIUM collaborations, and knowledge-sharing mechanisms.

3.6 Sustainability Beyond the Project

GRAPHIA's approach to sustainability focuses on ensuring the continued relevance, accessibility, and usability of its outputs beyond the funded duration of the project. As outlined in the Description of Action, this includes both technical and organisational measures for long-term integration into European research infrastructures and reuse by diverse stakeholder communities (*DoA WP6; Sections 1.1.2, 1.2.2, and 2.2*).

Sustainability planning is led under **Task 6.3**, in collaboration with technical leads and partners responsible for each KER. These activities are grounded in the FAIR and Judicious, Unbiased, Safe, Transparent (JUST) principles.

The **FAIR principles** guide the development of all project outputs, ensuring integration with established federations such as **EOSC** and **SSHOC** (*DoA Task 4.2*).

GRAPHIA also promotes the **JUST principles**, as introduced in the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA 1.0), which govern user behaviour in relation to data. This is achieved through dataset-level annotation, supporting ethical reflection and accountability in the use of shared data resources (*DoA Section 1.2.7*).

Several sustainability mechanisms are in place or under development:

- **SSH Knowledge Graph (KER1)**. A governance and sustainability model is being developed to ensure the continued availability, maintenance and community use of the SSH Knowledge Graph beyond the project period. Stewardship models are under consideration, including integration with OPERAS, alignment with EOSC-related entities, or support from a coordinated consortium. The framework will be validated and refined through stakeholder engagement in the second project phase.
- **Open-source tools and technical components (KER2, KER4, KER5)**. These tools are made available under permissive open-source licences (MIT), with supporting documentation, APIs and containerised deployments. They are hosted via institutional Git repositories (e.g. OPERAS) and will be listed in the SSH Open Marketplace and other EOSC-aligned catalogues. Sustainability is further supported by contributions from the research community, and potential reuse through follow-on projects.
- **Zenodo Community Repository**. A dedicated Zenodo community has been established for GRAPHIA. It provides a persistent, citable archive of datasets, deliverables and software packages, supporting long-term discoverability and reuse even after project completion.
- **Institutional and infrastructure partner commitments**. Partners such as OPERAS, CNR and PSNC have committed to ongoing hosting and curation of selected outputs, which will remain accessible through institutional service platforms and infrastructure catalogues.
- **Validation through Innovation Prototyping Labs (IPLs)**. GRAPHIA's IPLs provide a mechanism for real-world validation and sustainability testing. They engage external stakeholders to evaluate the relevance and usability of project outputs, and will inform final documentation and integration strategies.

Task 6.1 leads the overarching innovation management process across all KERs, including exploitation readiness, the KER Champions process, and the IPL methodology. Industry engagement and commercialisation pathways are addressed

under Task 6.3 and reported in Section 3.7. The two tasks are tightly coupled and jointly chaired by ICF.

Sustainability planning will continue to evolve throughout the project and will be reviewed regularly. A refined strategy, including confirmed governance structures and post-project hosting arrangements, will be presented in the final policy deliverable D6.4 at Month 36.

3.7 Progress on Engagement, Outreach and Commercialisation

Task 6.3 addresses industry engagement, commercialisation pathways and market readiness for GRAPHIA's exploitable results. Activities at M18 centre on the construction of a stakeholder registry and engagement strategy, the outcomes of the Call for Pilots, the pilot workshops held in April 2026, the assembly of a portfolio of business models per KER, engagement routes into Common European Data Spaces, and the [CERN IdeaSquare Journal of Experimental Innovation](#) (CIJ) special issue.

Stakeholder registry and mapping. A stakeholder registry, paired with systematic analysis of its contents, is the primary instrument for ensuring that industry engagement is evidence-based, transparent and inclusive. The consortium has assessed several methodologies (including the Saliency Model and the Power/Interest Grid) and adopted the Power/Interest Grid as the working approach. The Grid maps stakeholders by their power (influence) and interest (stakes) in respect of project impact and outputs, sorting them into four quadrants and guiding the prioritisation of engagement effort. The registry was built by extending the initial mapping carried out for the DoA: identifying, analysing and characterising the individuals, groups and organisations with an interest, influence or stake in GRAPHIA, and grouping them into three categories, each split between internal and external stakeholders:

- **Academia and scholarly communication:** SSH researchers; universities and research institutes; scientific and digital libraries; academic journal editorial boards; providers of open repositories and research data; startups and SMEs working in AI and Knowledge Graphs; academic publishers.
- **Industry:** companies using cultural and social data; companies integrating AI and LLM outputs; cloud providers and system integrators; commercial publishers.

- **Society and public organisations:** social and educational organisations; public institutions; government agencies and policymakers; standardisation bodies and European infrastructures.

Working groups. Stakeholder engagement under Task 6.3 is organised through three working groups, each led by the partner closest to the relevant community:

- **Academia** (lead: PSNC, Marcin Plociennik). Focus on European SSH research communities, research infrastructures, and doctoral and early-career networks.
- **Industry** (lead: Cyprus Institute, Athanasios Koutoupas). Focus on European technology SMEs and platform operators, drawing on the Call for Pilots cohort and ICF's and other partners' connections with the wider Knowledge Graph network.
- **Public Organisations and Society** (lead: OPERAS, Elena Sokolova). Focus on cultural heritage institutions, public bodies, scholarly publishing, and civil-society users of SSH data and AI tools.

Asynchronous coordination of stakeholder engagement across the three working groups is run through dedicated Mattermost channels (stakeholders-academia, stakeholders-industry, stakeholders-public), reducing reliance on meeting-by-meeting updates and providing partners with a persistent record of contact. Stakeholder feedback gathered through the use-case template (described in detail in section 2.5.2 *Call for Pilots*) and working-group notes is fed back into the KER Champions Working Document, the IPL2 content planning process, and the forthcoming updates to the exploitation strategy.

Engagement methods. Across the three working groups, the consortium applies a graduated set of engagement methods, matched to the maturity of the relationship and the type of stakeholder:

- Establishing initial contact.
- Validating stakeholder expectations of GRAPHIA and the project's value proposition for the stakeholder.
- Presentation and consultation through requirements workshops and interviews.
- Co-creation pilots, offering companies an opportunity to shape tools before final versions.

- First-look demonstrators, with access to pre-final tools and a structured feedback loop.
- Business-model workshops, exploring viable models including licensing, SaaS and consultancy packages.
- Exploitation agreements covering direct commercialisation, service uptake, licences and IPR-based product development;
- Transition-to-market activities, including Letters of Intent and exploitation partnerships.
- The Industry Hub.
- Webinar attendance and 3rd party events.

Portfolio of business models. The consortium has agreed that GRAPHIA will deliver a portfolio of business models rather than a single business plan, with one model per KER or cluster of KERs. Sustainability modes identified to date include: marketplace listing with community maintenance (KER1, KER5); collaborative open-source stewardship (KER2, KER4); institutional anchoring by RI partners (KER3); and fee-based consultancy and use-case licensing (KER6 and per-case exploitation). Early market signals from the Call for Pilots, combined with KER-specific sustainability input collected through the KER Champions process under Task 6.1, will be consolidated into a draft business portfolio during the second reporting period and reported in D6.4.

Industry-facing events. A GRAPHIA Federation Workshop, organised by Foxcub/CNRS on SSH Knowledge Graph federation architecture, has been scheduled as a cross-WP activity relevant to KER1 and KER5. Industry engagement during the first IPL (Zagreb, October 2025), including the participation of Infobip, has been captured in a dedicated section embedded in this deliverable, call for pilots workshops as well as individual meetings have been held.

A full list of industry contacts engaged throughout the various events and efforts is provided in Appendix 7.5 *Industry Participation and Collaboration*.

Participation in Common European Data Spaces. Engagement routes through T3.3 are being coordinated by OPERAS and OAPEN, positioning GRAPHIA services for visibility in SSH-relevant data-space initiatives. Specific entry points will be reported in deliverable 6.4.

CIJ Special Issue. A special issue of the [CERN IdeaSquare Journal of Experimental Innovation](#), edited by Michela Magas and Andrew Dubber from ICF (task leader for

6.1 and 6.3), has received 26 article manuscripts, which are currently under external peer review. The issue serves both as a dissemination route and as an industry-facing publication for methods and insights emerging from the IPL process.

Coordination with Task 6.1. Task 6.3 activity is tightly coupled to the KER Champions process under Task 6.1. Where a KER shows commercial potential, engagement with industrial actors and licensing considerations are routed through the Task 6.3 team; where sustainability is primarily academic or infrastructural, it remains with Task 6.1. The two tasks are jointly chaired by ICF.

Engagement activity is expected to intensify in the run-up to IPL2 (Brussels, September 2026), which is being designed to deepen engagement with the three working-group communities and to surface new commercial and institutional contacts.

3.8 Progress on Engagement through Innovation Prototyping Labs

IPLs are a central mechanism within GRAPHIA for engaging stakeholders, validating outputs and shaping long-term exploitation strategies. Designed as interactive and interdisciplinary events, the IPLs connect technical development with real-world applications, drawing input from a broad range of users, experts and infrastructure actors. They also contribute directly to WP6 and link to activities in WP2, WP3 and WP5.

GRAPHIA is set to deliver a **series of three IPLs** across the project duration. Each event is intended to progressively build towards wider uptake, reuse, and sustainability of project outputs.

As of Month 18, the following has been achieved:

- The **first IPL was delivered on 1–3 October 2025** in **Zagreb, Croatia**, co-located with a GRAPHIA consortium meeting and project workshops. The event provided the first major opportunity for partners to present and test project outputs with external stakeholders and is documented in a dedicated Executive Summary embedded in this deliverable.
- Planning was carried out in collaboration with the **LUMEN project**, ensuring alignment with European policy agendas on responsible AI, innovation ecosystems and infrastructure integration. The co-location of events increased impact and encouraged cross-project knowledge exchange.

- The [full report with an anonymised list of participants](#) has been published in the GRAPHIA Zenodo community.
- The IPL format included:
 - Hands-on technical workshops
 - Co-design sessions
 - Pilot demonstrations
 - Conference-style presentations
 - Hybrid-format engagement with invited external participants and the broader public
- Stakeholder engagement was carried out with SSH research infrastructures, cultural heritage institutions, scholarly publishers and public-sector users of data and AI tools. Participants interacted directly with outputs from the GRAPHIA use cases and contributed to future design and governance models.
- Representatives from [Infobip](#), a European technology unicorn founded in Croatia with a strong global reach, joined the first IPL. Infobip is a recognised digital communications leader with 75 offices worldwide. The company prioritised staff time to participate in the workshops and to engage with the GRAPHIA team on the application of knowledge graphs in real-world communication systems. The company founder and CTO welcomed the consortium with a dedicated in-person address. Their presence provided a valuable opportunity for industry-academia dialogue and knowledge exchange and contributed commercial and infrastructure perspectives to the workshop sessions.
- Thematic areas addressed included:
 - Cross-infrastructure data enrichment workflows
 - Governance and ethics in federated data
 - Multilingual AI and responsible knowledge extraction
 - Interoperability across SSH domains

Planning for the **second IPL** is now under way. IPL2 will be hosted at CNRS offices in Brussels on 14–18 September 2026, co-organised with the LUMEN project. A dedicated IPL Content Meeting series has been launched, distinct from the IPL Committee that covers logistics and governance. At the first content meeting (24 March 2026), 14 partner organisations participated and agreed KPI targets: at least

six task-focused workshops, CIJ publications, podcast episodes, structured feedback into technical work packages, and industry engagement. A partner input form has been circulated for asynchronous contributions towards IPL2 programme design. The **third IPL** will be held in the final year of the project and will be tailored to the evolving state of project outputs, supporting iteration, deeper prototyping, cross-sectoral engagement, and policy alignment.

The IPLs play a key role in GRAPHIA's exploitation strategy by grounding technical development in community needs and institutional realities. Outcomes from each IPL feed directly into the refinement of project deliverables, including the sustainability plan described in Section 3.6, the industry engagement activity in Section 3.7, and the evolving communication and engagement strategy.

3.9 Planned Discussions and Next Steps

As this is an updated version of the deliverable 6.2 submitted at Month 18, some elements of GRAPHIA's long-term exploitation strategy remain staged for development during the next phase of the project. These next steps are aligned with the work plan for WP6 and contribute directly to the refinement of sustainability, governance, and uptake strategies.

The following activities are planned:

- **Governance model for the SSH Knowledge Graph (KER1).** A draft sustainability and governance framework for the SSH Knowledge Graph will be finalised during the second reporting period. This includes clarification of long-term roles for hosting, curation, and interoperability management. Options under review include stewardship by OPERAS, a dedicated consortium, or alignment with the EOSC Innovation Centre being developed by ICF through the LUMEN project. Final recommendations will be included in the updated strategy under Deliverable D6.4 (M36).
- **Sustained contribution and community stewardship of open-source tools.** Planning is under way to support the continued use, contribution to, and maintenance of GRAPHIA's technical components (KERs 2, 4, and 5). This includes identifying appropriate governance models for open repositories, contribution guidelines and infrastructure integration. These plans will be

informed by real-world piloting during the use cases and refined through stakeholder engagement at IPL2 and IPL3.

- **Integration pathways into EOSC and federated catalogues.** The project will define clear publication and integration routes for tools and datasets into EOSC-facing infrastructures, particularly the SSH Open Marketplace and aligned metadata services. This will involve technical preparation and engagement with catalogue maintainers in the next reporting period. A first step in this direction is the workflow published by the GRAPHIA team in collaboration with the [ATRIUM](#) project, which presents ways of using GoTriple data for SSH data analytics tasks (see "[Using GoTriple data for your SSH data science tasks](#)"). This workflow describes the datasets used by the GRAPHIA team for the training of LLMs in the WP4 work package, together with the code that produced them by querying the information of the GoTriple platform. It can be considered a good practice of sharing knowledge openly, beyond the boundaries of the GRAPHIA project.

These activities represent key steps toward a robust, participatory and sustainable exploitation strategy. Updates and validated plans will be included in the final version of this deliverable as part of deliverable 6.4.

4. Progress Towards GRAPHIA's Specific Objectives

As a result of the first 18 months of the project, major progress towards some of the Specific Objectives has been achieved as shown in the tables below.

SO3 (Create a collaborative space between SSH RIs and Industry to foster value-added services co-creation)		
Achievement indicators:	Means of verification:	Links:
#IPL labs: 1	Official documentation or reports for first IPLs.	Zenodo report

# industrial partners participating in workshops & training: 62	Workshop/training participant list.	Appendix 7.5 <i>Industry Participation and Collaborations</i>
# use cases based on the SSH KG/# pilots/prototypes:	Published use cases for the SSH KG/ Entry added to the Industry Digital Hub.	12 use cases added to the Industry Hub

Table 6. SO3 details

SO4 (Accelerating industries' update of advanced technologies for social and cultural data markets)		
Achievement indicators:	Means of verification:	Links:
# industrial partners participating in workshops & trainings: 62	Attendance records and training materials.	Appendix 7.5 <i>Industry Participation and Collaborations</i> YouTube channel
# industrial collaborations: 20	Established agreements published on the GRAPHIA website.	12 use cases added to the Industry Hub

Table 7. SO4 details

As per the below two charts, overall, the industry collaboration and participation spans across Europe but also outside. Most organisations were SMEs with some large enterprises and consulting organisations.

Figure 9. Industry collaboration/participation geographical distribution

Figure 10. Industry collaboration/participation organisational type

5. Communication

To support the project overall, on top of the dissemination activities from section 2, a list of additional communication measures and indicators has been created, mainly focusing on amplifying the messages that will be shared across the target groups (figure 1). Table 5 contains only some of the examples of messages that will be shared as more are expected to be added as the project progresses.

Messages	Activity & Channels/Tools	Indicator	Progress so far
SSH KG: Forge connections between SSH data for new and improved research or business application	Social media posts on project and project partners' social media profiles	# of posts by the end of the project on the official project social media channels LinkedIn = B:200/T:250/S:300 Bluesky= B:100/T:130/S:150	LinkedIn posts through GRAPHIA profile 113 posts Bluesky posts through GRAPHIA profile 104
LL4SSH: Your personal SSH research assistant			
Instrumentations: Ability to serve enhanced digitisation practices and applications in various sectors		# of posts by the end of the projects on project partners' social media channels LinkedIn = B:150/T:200/S:250 Bluesky = B:30/T:50/S:70	LinkedIn posts through partners or other profiles 195 Bluesky posts through partners or other profiles 73
SSH Citation Index: Better track SSH research and gain visibility for it	Mailing list communications	# of sign-ups B:100/T:150/S:200	393 sign-ups
Interoperability Framework: Maximise data potential; Streamline sharing and collaboration; Stopping to reinvent the wheel	Newsletters	# of newsletters sent to the project mailing list by the end of the project B:15/T:20/S:25	14 newsletters
Use Cases: Individual value		# of project partners' newsletters that mentioned the project by the end of the project B:10/T:12/S:14	20 newsletter

propositions defined; Visibility in the Industry Digital Hub	Events	# of announcements about the events across the project's duration (workshops, webinars, final event, 3rd party events, trainings) B:30/T:40/S:50	29 announcements
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Table 8. Communication measures with KPIs

At the time of writing the proposal for this project, the partners envisioned using the platform X/Twitter as the main social media platform, accompanied by LinkedIn in a secondary role. However, given the development since the beginning of 2024 and after noticing stakeholders leaving X/Twitter due to various reasons (political, personal or other), it has become evident that the chosen social media platforms need to be revisited. For this purpose, a short internal discussion as well as consultation with the GRAPHIA Project Officer allowed us to identify LinkedIn as the primary platform within the established channels and Bluesky as the dedicated new platform replacing X/Twitter in a secondary role. This was also supported by a very positive initial interaction with the GRAPHIA profile on LinkedIn and an increased number of followers.

The events announcements KPI only includes the events listed on the dedicated GRAPHIA page [here](#) to not double count the social media posts too. However if we take those into consideration as well, the announcements number is much higher.

6. Conclusion

The DEC Plan document represents an agreed-upon methodology across the GRAPHIA project that guides the activities of all project partners when they engage with the community, communicate about its results, and plan the exploitation activities. It is crucial in supporting the impact of the project and complements the Communication Kit developed separately. All project partners involved in WP6 and several partners outside that WP have collaborated in creating this document. It is intended as a living document with formal updates foreseen in M18 and M36 of the project.

7. Appendix

7.1 Zenodo Records

Title	Published	Views	Downloads
D6.1 Communication Kit	March 31, 2025	209	272
D5.1 User Personas and Scenarios	July 7, 2025	229	197
D1.1 Data Management Plan	September 5, 2025	82	54
D6.2 Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan	September 5, 2025	72	53
Helping SSH Researchers to Explore and Exploit Knowledge Graphs through Artificial Intelligence: the GRAPHIA Project	October 7, 2025	374	165
GRAPHIA & LUMEN Innovation Prototyping Lab	October 21, 2025	64	17
Building LUMIS together	October 21, 2025	73	59
Sustainability Pathways. The road to sustainability - business models for LUMEN outcomes	October 21, 2025	65	43
Making Knowledge Graphs Tangible: Interactive Demonstration and Q&A Session	October 21, 2025	59	48
Designing compelling use cases for the LUMEN Interdisciplinary Meta-Search	October 21, 2025	75	46
The LUMEN Data Mesh Framework. Focus on the Federated Data Sharing Governance Layer	October 21, 2025	55	41
Language as an Interface: Using LLMs for Knowledge Graph Exploration in the Social Sciences and Humanities	October 21, 2025	79	57
IPL: Prototyping tools for knowledge exploration: Project interoperability	October 21, 2025	63	53
Building the GRAPHIA Ontology together	October 21, 2025	114	74

CERN IdeaSquare Journal of Experimental Innovation. Special Issue on 'Co-Creation'	October 21, 2025	66	40
1st GRAPHIA Webinar - Introduction to Knowledge Graphs	October 22, 2025	76	57
GoTriple Language Identification Benchmark Datasets	November 4, 2025	36	37
odoma-ch/gotriple-data-utils: Version 1.0.0	November 7, 2025	62	5
GRAPHIA Infographic	November 21, 2025	128	90
Exploration of Research Impact through IMeTo. Supporting Societal Technology Transfer	December 4, 2025	129	69
Draft Catalogue of Innovative Workflows for Data Management and Connection to the SSH KG	December 16, 2025	199	122
GoTriple metadata dataset	January 8, 2026	442	2844
D2.2 Technical Architecture	January 12, 2026	289	233
D4.2 Report on Existing Datasets, Methods and Tools for the SSH Citation Index	January 12, 2026	188	118
D2.1 GRAPHIA Ontology	February 11, 2026	176	123
GRAPHIA & LUMEN Innovation Prototyping Lab 2025 Report	February 27, 2026	81	65
An Introduction to Large Language Models through GRAPHIA	March 23, 2026	200	95
Why a Knowledge Graph for SSH? Concrete Use Cases with GRAPHIA	March 23, 2026	62	38
GRAPHIA_WP3_D3.1_AppendixA.json	April 9, 2026	29	4
D3.1 Catalogue of Next-Gen SSH Instruments and Tools	April 10, 2026	89	63
Beyond SPARQL: Towards Conversation-based Access to Knowledge Graphs in GRAPHIA	April 22, 2026	57	43
GRAPHIA: Advancing SSH Knowledge through a Collaborative Knowledge Graph Ecosystem	April 28, 2026	77	51
QLever Evaluation Report	May 4, 2026	19	13
GRAPHIA Publisher/Author Use Cases	May 4, 2026	25	15

7.2 Blog Posts

Title	Link	Published
GRAPHIA Project Launched in January 2025	https://opencitations.hypotheses.org/3869	Mar 2025
CHC w europejskim projekcie GRAPHIA	https://operas.pl/2025/03/27/chc-w-europejskim-projekcie-graphia/	Mar 2025
GRAPHIA Project: Pioneering a Unified Knowledge Graph for Social Sciences and Humanities	https://graphia-ssh.eu/news-blog/graphia-project-pioneering-a-unified-knowledge-graph-for-social-sciences-and-humanities/	Apr 2025
GRAPHIA: Keeping Social Sciences and Humanities Researchers at the Heart of its Design Process	https://graphia-ssh.eu/news-blog/graphia-keeping-social-sciences-and-humanities-researchers-at-the-heart-of-its-design-process/	Ap 2025
Introducing GRAPHIA use cases	https://lab.operas-eu.org/2025/05/15/introducing-graphia-use-cases/	May 2025
Introducing TALLMesh, Our Tool for AI-Powered Thematic Analysis	https://lab.operas-eu.org/2025/07/25/introducing-tallmesh-our-tool-for-ai-powered-thematic-analysis/	Jul 2025
The EHRI Use-Case for GRAPHIA: LLM-assisted Information Discovery for Heterogeneous Multilingual Data	https://lab.operas-eu.org/2025/08/18/the-ehri-use-case-for-graphia-llm-assisted-information-discovery-for-heterogeneous-multilingual-data/	Aug 2025
Genius Loci & GRAPHIA: Giving Shape to the Question “Where?”	https://lab.operas-eu.org/2025/08/29/genius-loci-graphia-giving-shape-to-the-question-where/	Aug 2025
Innovation Prototyping Lab 2025	https://graphia-ssh.eu/news-blog/innovation-prototyping-lab-2025/	Sep 2025
Mapping Cross-Project Functionalities – an OPERAS Innovation Lab workshop for LUMEN x	https://graphia-ssh.eu/news-blog/knowledge-graph-for-ssh-enriched-with-a	Sep 2025

GRAPHIA	rtificial-intelligence-released-2/	
Introducing Quagga: A Community Effort to Collect Scattered SSH Knowledge Graph Resources	https://graphia-ssh.eu/news-blog/introducing-quagga-a-community-effort-to-collect-scattered-ssh-knowledge-graph-resources/	Oct 2025
Mapping Cross-Project Functionalities: When Innovation Meets Collaboration	https://lab.operas-eu.org/2025/11/17/mapping-cross-project-functionalities-when-innovation-meets-collaboration/	Nov 2025
Co-Designing GRAPHIA: SSH Researchers Shape the Future of Knowledge Graph Interfaces	https://graphia-ssh.eu/news-blog/co-designing-graphia-ssh-researchers-shape-the-future-of-knowledge-graph-interfaces/	Dec 2025
GRAPHIA Publishes the Draft Catalogue of Innovative Workflows	https://graphia-ssh.eu/news-blog/graphia-publishes-the-draft-catalogue-of-innovative-workflows/	Dec 2025
What Do Knowledge Graphs Bring to OA Publishing – A Reflection	https://graphia-ssh.eu/news-blog/what-do-knowledge-graphs-bring-to-oa-publishing-a-reflection/	Jan 2026
Innovation Prototyping Labs: Making Space for Higher-order Questions	https://graphia-ssh.eu/news-blog/innovation-prototyping-labs-making-space-for-higher-order-questions/	Jan 2026
All you need to know to begin with Knowledge Graphs: GRAPHIA introduces a new webinar series	https://lab.operas-eu.org/2026/02/04/all-you-need-to-know-to-begin-with-knowledge-graphs-graphia-introduces-a-new-webinar-series/	Feb 2026
Tworzemy graf wiedzy	https://operas.pl/2026/03/05/tworzymy-graf-wiedzy/	Mar 2026
Researchers Share, GRAPHIA Listens: Insights and Actions from our Latest SSH Survey	https://graphia-ssh.eu/news-blog/researchers-share-graphia-listens-insights	Apr 2026

	-and-actions-from-our-latest-ssh-survey/	
GRAPHIA's SSH Federated Knowledge Graph: Vision and Goal	https://graphia-ssh.eu/news-blog/graphias-ssh-federated-knowledge-graph-vision-and-goal/	Apr 2026
IMeTo: A Scalable AI Workflow for Documenting SSH Research Impact	https://graphia-ssh.eu/news-blog/ime-to-a-scalable-ai-workflow-for-documenting-ssh-research-impact/	Apr 2026
GRAPHIA's SSH Federated Knowledge Graph: The Role of GoTriple	https://graphia-ssh.eu/news-blog/graphias-ssh-federated-knowledge-graph-the-role-of-gotriple/	May 2026
Welcome to the GRAPHIA Industry Hub: Connecting Research, Innovation, and Impact	https://graphia-ssh.eu/news-blog/welcome-to-the-graphia-industry-hub-connecting-research-innovation-and-impact/	Jun 2026

7.3 GRAPHIA Videos

Title	Link	Published	Type	Views
1st GRAPHIA Webinar - Introduction to Knowledge Graphs	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lgeSdd3cOf0&t=2s	Oct 2025	Webinar	157
IPL Day 1 Welcome and Intro	https://youtu.be/NiP8ICFiD1A?si=pdM-mD4yEyW-yMQP	Nov 2025	IPL event	51
IPL Day 1 LUMEN x GRAPHIA: Mapping cross-project functionalities	https://youtu.be/Li3ER9OEwKU?si=g8BTEcCWV4SNGRw3	Nov 2025	IPL event	25
Day 1 LUMEN Governance: Building Shared Governance Models for Interdisciplinary	https://youtu.be/44HBH1mOreA?si=EzwPTkkZqE56XROz	Nov 2025	IPL event	18

Discovery				
Day 1 Global Brainstorming: Innovation Through Co-creation (CERN CIJ Co-Creation Special Issue)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WEakfQ5tFf0&t=2091s	Nov 2025	IPL event	27
Day 2 Welcome and Intro - Project Interoperability	https://youtu.be/Dgr_wk938o?si=fMby5ZUsTh5iG3mM	Nov 2025	IPL event	13
Day 2 Designing Compelling Use Cases for the LUMEN Interdisciplinary Meta-Search	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EJi7qUO2boc&t=240s	Nov 2025	IPL event	14
Day 2 Designing LUMIS – From User Stories to a First Minimum Viable Product	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Lxmq22mpids	Nov 2025	IPL event	14
Day 2 Making Knowledge Graphs Tangible: Interactive Demonstration and Q&A Session	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jzN5JtSbZxl&t=228s	Nov 2025	IPL event	42
Day 2 Building the GRAPHIA Ontology together	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Bit8Lf3tmns	Nov 2025	IPL event	24
Day 2 Hybrid AI and the Future of Semantic Research & Industry	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1x39YnvramA	Nov 2025	IPL event	44
Day 3 Welcome and Intro by Infobip: One Communication Platform. Billions of Conversations.	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OkfaQQ4O9-A&t=131s	Nov 2025	IPL event	15
Day 3 Language as an Interface	https://www.youtube.com	Nov 2025	IPL event	52

	m/watch?v=Ch8aDk435Hg			
Day 3 The Road to Sustainability - Business Models for LUMEN Outcomes	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tbimMnZmqI4	Nov 2025	IPL event	18
Day 3 Part 1 of From Chatbots to Agentic Systems: Designing Conversational Experiences with AI	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Ng6u7G8ArFY	Nov 2025	IPL event	18
Day 3 Part 2 of From Chatbots to Agentic Systems: Designing Conversational Experiences with AI	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mhf7RsCUseE&t=2149s	Nov 2025	IPL event	20
Day 3 Part 3 of From Chatbots to Agentic Systems: Designing Conversational Experiences with AI	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QKZfZUbtweQ&t=15s	Nov 2025	IPL event	15
Day 3 Part 4 of From Chatbots to Agentic Systems: Designing Conversational Experiences with AI	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vaF5VStpmSo&t=294s	Nov 2025	IPL event	30
Introducing Quagga: A Community Effort to Collect Scattered SSH Knowledge Graph Resources	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SJQODItpiNw	Nov 2025	Instructions video	152
GRAPHIA 2025 Highlights	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Z2oekk43OSY	Dec 2025	End of year message	45
Why a Knowledge Graph for	https://www.youtube.com	Feb 2026	Webinar	216

SSH? Concrete Use Cases with GRAPHIA	m/watch?v=YLr7W5IU5ck&t=2s			
An Introduction to Large Language Models through GRAPHIA	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Vg1-BF6donA&t=976s	Mar 2026	Webinar	320
Beyond SPARQL: towards conversation-based access to knowledge graphs in GRAPHIA	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZOTwwGenmBA	Apr 2026	Webinar	95

7.4 GRAPHIA 3rd Party Events

Title of Event	Type	Location	Timeframe
AI and LLMs as tools for open scholarly communication in social sciences and humanities. Organised by OPERAS Tools & Platforms special interest group. GRAPHIA participated with a short presentation.	Workshop	Online	24/02/2025
Metadata-based research in Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences	Workshop	Prague	04-05/03/2025
AI for Science	PPT	Krakow	21/03/2025
FORTMED 2025	PPT	Caserta	10-12/04/2025
Le monde en trois dimensions	PPT	Paris	19/05/2025
Workshop on Open Citations & Open Scholarly Metadata	Workshop	Bologna	28-29/05/2025
Digital Humanities Benelux	PPT	Amsterdam	03-06/06/2025
Digital Humanities Lisbon	Poster	Lisbon	14-18/07/2025
Enriching Digital Heritage with LLMs and Linked Open Data	Workshop	Leiden	08-12/09/2025
IEEE International Conference on Cyber Humanities	PPT	Florence	08-10/09/2025
Open Science Conference	Poster	Hamburg	08-09/10/2025
Working Group 5 "Sustaining Infrastructures" of the	PPT	Online	30/09/2025

Barcelona Declaration on Open research Information			
New Approaches for Extracting Heterogeneous Reference Data	PPT	Frankfurt & online	04/11/2025
Project partners will be presenting at the British Computer Society's Special Interest Group in Human Computer Interaction Conference	PPT	Cardiff	11/11/2025
GROBID workshop	PPT	Paris	27/11/2025
GoTriple's developments: Knowledge graphs and responsible metrics for SSH assessment	PPT	Online	03/12/2025
CNR / E-RIHS meeting	PPT	Rome	05-06/02/2026
SCOLIA 2026	Workshop	Delft	02/04/2026
Co-Data: Cultivating Effective Human-LLM Collaboration for Collaborative Data Processing	Workshop	Barcelona	13/04/2026
From Generation to Simulation: Responsible Use of AI Personas in Human-Centered Design and Research	Workshop	Barcelona	13/04/2026
AI4LAM Community Call	PPT	Online	21/04/2026
Journées 2026 de l'EquipEx+ ESPADON.	PPT	Paris	20/05/2026
OPERAS conference	Poster	Warsaw	20/05/2026
OPERAS conference	Panel	Warsaw	21/05/2026
CiteX 2026	Workshop	Frankfurt	28-29/05/2026

7.5 Industry Participation and Collaborations

Source	Year	Organisation	Type	Location	Role	Number (individual organisations)
1st webinar	2025	ConsultMU Ltd	Consultancy / Private Company	UK	Participant	6
		Freelance Project Manager	Individual Contractor /	Undisclosed		

			Consultancy			
		Genius Loci	SME	Italy		
		T&F	Large commercial company	UK		
		Odoma	SME	Switzerland		
		Net7	SME	Italy		
IPL 1	2025	better.day	SME	USA	Participant	30
		Genius Loci	SME	Switzerland		
		e Science Data Factory	SME	France		
		Foxcub	SME	France		
		Net7	SME	Italy		
		Metaphacts	SME	Germany		
		Odoma	SME	Switzerland		
		Nutri Medik Doo	SME	Serbia		
		Kanegi	SME	India		
		VOID:Projects	SME	UK		
		Palga	SME	The Netherlands		
		Seedlings	SME	UK		
		BHC	SME	Germany		
		skerratt.com	SME	UK		
		Paradigma Exponential Hub	Industry / Innovation Hub	UK		
		Crastinus	SME	UK		
		Libelium	SME	Spain		
		Infobip	Large commercial company	Croatia		
		Velocamp	SME	Not		

				available		
		Klump Subtopia/creARTiv e	Incubator / Creative Industry	Sweden		
		Imperative Space	SME	UK		
		Enviro Data	SME	Sweden		
		Sensorica	SME	UK		
		SOURCEKID	SME	Sweden		
		Never Get Rid of Noise	SME	Spain		
		MTF Labs	SME	Sweden		
		Freelance Consultant	Individual Contractor / Consultancy	Germany		
		Freelance Consultant	Individual Contractor / Consultancy	UK		
		Freelance Consultant	Individual Contractor / Consultancy	UK		
		Freelance Consultant	Individual Contractor / Consultancy	Info not available		
Industrial use cases from 2025	2025	Infobip	Large commercial company	Croatia	In progress	4
		Taylor & Francis	Large commercial company	UK	Published	
		Genius Loci	SME	Italy	Published	
		Metaphacts	SME	Germany	Published	
2nd webinar	2026	Freelance Consultant	Individual Contractor /	Germany	Participant	5

			Consultancy			
		Freelance Consultant	Individual Contractor / Consultancy	Ukraine		
		Odoma	SME	Switzerland		
		e-science data factory	SME	France		
		John Benjamins Publishing Company	SME	Netherlands		
1st call for pilots use cases from 2026	2026	OiPub	SME	Malta	Participant	13
		Data ScienceTech Institute	SME	France	Participant	
		Brepols Publishers	SME	Belgium	Published	
		CONSELLO D'A FABLA ARAGONESA	Private organisation	Spain	Participant	
		LIBARGO	SME	Spain	Participant	
		Archipanion	SME	Switzerland	Participant	
		Sigma Squared	SME	Greece	Published	
		L'Harmattan Open Access	SME	Hungary	Published	
		Ubiquity Press	SME	UK	Published	
		Univeresitat Politècnica de València	Private organisation	Spain	Participant	
		OpenMinds	SME	Sweden	Published	
		Persee (2 use cases)	Public organisations collaborating with commercial publishers	France	Published	

		Polish Press Agency	SME	Poland	Published	
3rd webinar	2026	Genius Loci	SME	Italy	Participant	14
		Odoma	SME	Switzerland		
		e-Science Data Factory	SME	France		
		lovevolv inc	SME	Switzerland		
		CiphezTech Digital Solutions	SME	Nigeria		
		ANT AUTOMATION LLC	SME	Undisclosed		
		Slaughter and May	SME	UK		
		ACERT Consulting	Individual Contractor / Consultancy	Chile		
		Omni Iota Science	SME	Malta		
		ConsultMU Ltd	Individual Contractor / Consultancy	UK		
		Kennedys	SME	UK		
		Powerbuilderexperts	Individual Contractor / Consultancy	France		
		Wal Textile	SME	Pakistan		
Foxcub	SME	France				
4th webinar	2026	Semantic Generation	SME	US	Participant	12
		e-Science Data Factory	SME	France		
		Odoma	SME	Switzerland		
		Code Power	Individual Contractor / Consultancy	Poland		
		MTF Labs	SME	Sweden		

		Gale	SME	UK		
		Pensoft Publishers	SME	Bulgaria		
		CiphezTech Digital Solutions	SME	Undisclosed		
		Net7	SME	Italy		
		Enviro Data	SME	Sweden		
		Genius Loci	SME	Italy		
		Ubiquity Press	SME	UK		

Total number across all events without duplicates: 62